

DELIVERABLE 2.2

**REPORT ON FOOD-RELATED
POLICIES AND PLANNING
FRAMEWORKS IN THE EIGHT
CITY-REGIONS AND AT
NATIONAL LEVEL**

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report is one of the deliverables of the FoodCLIC project, an EU-funded project that focuses on creating resilient urban food environments. In particular, this is the outcome of Task 2.3 (Work Package 2), which aims to identify and assess current and upcoming urban food-related policies, planning frameworks and initiatives to change city-regions' food systems. This report is intended for city and local government officials, community organisations, NGOs, activist groups, farmers' groups, market organisations and practitioners in these city-regions and beyond. It also aims to spark transformative discussions and shed light on the significance of city-regions in driving food system transformation, emphasising the crucial role of (various forms of) Food Policy Networks (FPNs) in fostering sustainable, resilient, and equitable urban food systems.

There is a growing number of cities that have acknowledged the need to radically transform their food systems to make local, sustainable, and healthy food more available, affordable, and attractive to people (Moragues-Faus, 2021; Sonnino and Milbourne, 2022). To drive this transformation, cities are employing food-related policies, planning frameworks and initiatives (see, for example, Morgan, 2015; Mendes and Sonnino, 2018; Mooney, 2022). However, many cities face difficulties in developing such approaches and exhibit a limited and fragmented scope, concentrating on isolated concerns such as increased agricultural productivity or improved nutritional quality (e.g., Doernberg et al., 2019). As a result, cities often fail to address all three aspects of sustainability (i.e. social, economic and environmental), and overlook critical issues like existing power dynamics or social justice concerns (Sonnino, 2019; López Cifuentes et al. 2021; Sibbing and Candel, 2021).

This report aims to examine how eight city-regions address gaps and identify leverage points for transforming their local food systems. To this end, the report showcases a selection of food-related policies, planning frameworks, and initiatives with high potential for food system transformation, including their contribution to the establishment of FPNs and strengthening city-region food systems. In order to analyse the extent to which policies, planning frameworks and initiatives contribute to systemic change, the report uses the CLIC conceptual framework (see Sonnino and Milbourne, 2022).

The CLIC framework emphasises four key aspects to achieve food systems transformation:

Co-benefits between economic, social and environmental objectives;

Linkages between urban, peri-urban and rural areas;

Inclusion of marginalised and vulnerable groups in the design, implementation and monitoring of policies, planning frameworks and initiatives;

Connectivity between food system actors and priorities and other sectors and policies.

Using the CLIC framework, the assessment aims to identify the gaps, learning needs and potential leverage points for food system transformation in the following city-regions in which FoodCLIC Living Labs are operating: Aarhus (Denmark), Budapest (Hungary), Brasov (Romania), Berlin (Germany), Plain of Lucca (Italy), Barcelona (Spain), Amsterdam (Netherlands), and Lisbon (Portugal) (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Location of the city-regions

The next section provides more details on the mapping and gapping methodology used by the city-regions. Section 3 illustrates the results of the analysis process by focusing on each city-region. The analysis begins with mapping relevant food-related policies, planning frameworks, and initiatives, providing a contextual understanding of their respective characteristics such as evolution, outcomes, and impacts. The report presents exemplary cases that lead towards achieving environmental, social, and economic synergies through national and city-regional strategies and actions that promote co-benefits, urban-rural relations, inclusion of marginalised and vulnerable groups and connectivity with other scales, sectors, and institutions.

The work conducted by the Living Labs stands as the cornerstone of the report's data-driven insights, lending substantial weight to its findings outlined in the policy recommendations presented in Section 4.

These findings provide city and local government officials with a novel perspective from which to make well-informed decisions that closely align with the specific needs and challenges inherent to their respective city-regions. In a broader policy landscape, the report's focal points on sustainability co-benefits, inclusivity, urban-rural connections, and place-based approaches align with the overarching goals of the EU's sustainable food systems policy frameworks including [European Green Deal](#), the [Farm to Fork Strategy](#), [Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#) and [Circular Economy Action Plan](#). Furthermore, the report aligns with the forthcoming Sustainable Food System Law, reflecting the EU's commitment to holistic and transformative changes in food systems.

2. METHODOLOGY

This report is based on research data collected by the Living Labs of each city-region (i.e., local teams of practitioners and researchers involved in this project) in the first half of 2023 (see Table 1 for an overview). Data collection was based on the guidelines produced in the FoodCLIC project as part of Task 1.1 (see deliverable 1.1). These guidelines are divided into four steps and have guided the data collection and analysis of this task. This chapter describes the activities conducted during each of the four steps.

The **first step** focuses on the general identification of food(-related) policies, planning frameworks and initiatives. For a definition of these terms, we refer to Glossary of terms. To this end, the Living Labs used previous knowledge from their teams and conducted online searches using search platforms (e.g., Google) to collect official documents and online resources such as press articles about food-related policies, planning frameworks and initiatives. They also conducted broader web-based searches including official governments' and initiatives' websites. These searches produced a wide diversity of data, ranging from official documents like action plans, legislations, laws, and programmes to concept notes, and various published visions and mission statements from a range of organization's visions and missions. Two Living Labs have included scientific publications in their data collection - i.e. Berlin (Doernberg et al., 2019; Klebl et al., 2022; Vicente-Vicente et al., 2023) and Plain of Lucca (Grasseni, 2013; Arcuri et al., 2020; Arcuri et al., 2022; Pusceddu, 2020; Arcuri et al., forthcoming).

During the **second step**, the Living Labs identified a minimum of one national policy, two city-region policies, one planning framework, and ten initiatives within the city-region. The criteria for selection rested on achieving diversity in the case of selected policies, and addressing a spectrum of criteria for initiatives, which included:

- focus on marginalised and vulnerable groups, such as migrants, low income neighbourhoods and food-deprived people;
- showcasing innovative business models that take into account also the environmental and social aspects, and representing various facets of food environments such as retail (e.g. supermarkets, and food markets), hospitality (e.g. restaurants and cafes), institutional entities (e.g. public canteens), agri-food (e.g. farms), community and alternative networks (e.g. community gardens and kitchens), as well as wild food (e.g. fisheries and forestry).

To perform an in-depth analysis of the policies, planning frameworks and initiatives selected in Step 2, in **Step 3** the Living Labs completed a questionnaire based on the pillars of the CLIC framework.

Based on this filled-in mapping template, a gapping exercise followed in **Step 4**. The gapping template aimed at identifying gaps, leverage points and policy-makers' barriers and learning needs. The result of this exercise are summarized both in the policy recommendations (Chapter 4) and in the matrix (Annex 1). Since documents and online resources did not always provide the necessary information for these in-depth analyses, Living Labs engaged with key stakeholders in their city-regions through semi-structured and/or informal interviews (Table 1). The content of these interviews was structured based on the templates for steps 3 and 4 which they adapted according to their needs and local languages. Interviews were either audio recorded and transcribed or recorded in field notes. In the case of Berlin, the Living Lab also conducted two focus groups on food access and food justice respectively and an online survey with members of the Berlin Food Policy Council (Table 1). Other Living Labs like Aarhus, Amsterdam and Plain of Lucca complemented their data collection with participant observation at different events and site visits to projects (Table 1). In some cases, these approaches also served to identify further policies, planning frameworks and initiatives feeding into step 1. All collected data were analysed using the templates for steps 3 and 4 and the results are summarised in the next sections of this report.

Table 1: Overview of data collection methods used by each city-region

CITY-REGION	DATA COLLECTION METHODS		
	DOCUMENTS & ONLINE RESOURCES	INTERVIEWS	OTHERS
Aarhus	Documentation developed by governmental bodies (official sources). Search: Search platforms for initiatives like organisations and official sources' websites, Aarhus municipality for planning framework and initiatives and Ministries in charge of the documents for policies; online press articles and government and initiatives' websites.	2 semi-structured interviews with the initiatives MoCa Mad and Mellefolk Café (fieldnotes). 2 informal interviews with local grocery shop RAA Aarhus and Aarhus Planning Framework (fieldnotes).	Participant observation at presentations/workshops where the initiatives shared their activities (fieldnotes).

Amsterdam	<p>Vision documents, development plans, laws (crisis and recovery law), city council letters, city council decisions, year reports of initiatives, one bachelor thesis, PowerPoint presentations, pre-published policy briefs, online press, podcasts.</p> <p>Search: search platform (Google), institutions' websites, national, provincial, and municipal government websites, website 'spatial plans', online documentation of city councils ('notubiz').</p>	<p>3 semi-structured interviews with the initiatives</p> <p>TommyTomato, Boeren van Amstel and Boeren voor Buren (recorded).</p> <p>2 informal interviews with two initiatives Baking Lab and Voedseltuin IJplein (fieldnotes).</p>	Participant observation in initiatives activities (fieldnotes).
Barcelona	<p>Public and official documents like plans, strategies, and programmes.</p> <p>Search: search platform (Google); government and initiatives' websites.</p>	<p>6 semi-structured interviews with key actors in food policies, food-related researchers, and people in charge of relevant initiatives (3 recorded, 3 with field notes).</p>	
Berlin	<p>Food and health strategy documents, strategic concept notes, policy briefs.</p> <p>Scientific publications</p> <p>Sampling: Google Scholar & Scopus search for Berlin food/nutrition policy analysis; broader web-based search incl. google, daten.berlin.de, HWR research portal,</p>	<p>7 semi-structured interviews (3 recorded, 4 with fieldnotes) with: Berlin government administration (coordinator for interdepartmental community development initiative); German Federal Ministry (department leader); community</p>	<p>2 focus groups: (a) food access (representatives of Berlin Food Policy Council, national poverty network, Berlin food banks); and (b) food justice (activists, regional farmer, urban farmer, journalist, researchers, community, and event facilitators, and open to</p>

	parliamentary database, Berlin Senate websites.	health organisation (researcher and coordinator); community development initiative (2 Neighbourhood coordinators); agri-food researcher; school catering company (founder); indoor food market (head of market development); Berlin Food Policy Council (speaker).	interested city inhabitants). Survey (closed and open-ended questions) with Berlin Food Policy Council members about demographics, priorities, organisations of interest, and capacity for new and continued engagement of its members.
Brasov	Local council documents provided by Brasov Municipality legal office. Search: government's website.	20 informal interviews (fieldnotes) with political figures (e.g., vice mayor), different stakeholder owners from different food sectors, and local consumers.	
Budapest	Online resources (websites, articles) and official documents (action plans, strategies, programmes). Search: Google search platform.	10 informal interviews (fieldnotes) with local stakeholders, representatives of the districts and founders of the initiatives.	
Lisbon	Policy frameworks (plans, strategies, programmes) Search: official government websites, initiatives' websites	2 informal interviews (fieldnotes) with the initiatives Sintra Cresce Saudável and Heróis da Fruta.	

<p>Plain of Lucca</p>	<p>Initiatives' websites, public documents (such as policy documents and national laws and laws repositories), online resources (e.g., articles). Scientific publications. Search: research on google or flagged during interviews.</p>	<p>15 semi-structured interviews (recorded and field notes) with people previously engaged in the food policy network (representatives of local food initiatives or agrobusinesses and public servants from the municipalities of the Plain of Lucca and Capannori).</p>	<p>Participant observation in four local initiatives: an urban garden, food event, food coop, and food aid platform coordination meeting (fieldnotes).</p>
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3. CITY-REGIONS' POLICIES, PLANNING FRAMEWORKS AND INITIATIVES

This chapter summarises the data collected by the Living Labs in relation to the policies, planning frameworks and initiatives in their city-regions. The results are based on the analysis conducted using the CLIC framework. To enhance the readability of the tables concerning the presence of CLIC framework elements in various food-related policies, planning frameworks, and initiatives, symbols have been introduced. These symbols indicate where CLIC elements (*Co-benefits*, *Linkages*, *Inclusion*, and *Connectivity*) have been highlighted as key themes during the analysis. It is important to note that the meaning of CLIC symbols can differ, contingent on each city-region's local context and is intertwined with the broader discourse on food system transformation and city-region analysis.

3.1 AARHUS

Table 2: Overview of Aarhus Planning Frameworks, Policies and Initiatives

TYPE	TITLE	MAIN FOCUS	INITIATOR	TIME FRAME	CLIC			
					C	L	I	C
Planning Framework	Planning Department - Aarhus Municipality	Natural ecosystem, farmland, and renewable energy	Municipality	2019-2030				
National	Climate-friendly Dietary Guidelines	Guidelines to promote healthier and more climate-friendly diets	The Danish Veterinary and Food Administration	Since 1970				
National and city-level	Strategy for Food, Meals and Health	Better eating habits and health throughout life, affordable food options, food health	The Danish government	Since 2018				

		education, food market and labelling						
City-region policy	Green Transition in Aarhus: Climate Action Plan 2021-2024	CO2 reductions related to climate-friendly agriculture, Renewable energy, Circular economy, Mobility, Industry	Municipality	2024 (there will be a revised climate action plan 2025-2028)				
Initiative	4H	Activities to bring children closer to the origin of food and nature	4H global	Since 2004				
Initiative	Coop's policy on Environment and Climate	Range of activities to raise awareness of the climate and to support climate-friendly food	Coop Danmark	Since 2016				
Initiative	Derfor landmand	Instagram channel to raise awareness of young farmers' lives	The Innovation Centre for Organic Farming	Since 2021				
Initiative	Mellemfolk Cafeen	Cafe that offers mainly locally produced food and provide a space to share experiences and knowledge	Group of volunteers from Global Contact	Since 2013				
Initiative	MoCa Cafe	Canteen and cafe that provide local and organic food	Initiated by a Philosophy and based at Anthropology department at	2021 - 2025				

			Aarhus University					
Initiative	Raa Aarhus	Sustainable grocery store; connecting local food producers with chefs and consumers, promoting organic and locally sourced ingredients, reducing food packaging	Two biology students at Aarhus University	Since 2017				
Initiative	Skraldecafeen	Community-run socio-economic kitchen to recover discarded food and redistribute it to marginalised and vulnerable groups	Private individuals	Since 2015				

Food Policies and planning framework

The Aarhus city-region is a prominent hub for agriculture and food innovation in Denmark. Large retailers play a dominant role as primary food suppliers, yet small-scale farmers also participate via farmers' markets and direct sales. Furthermore, there are community gardens and allotments within the city and a number of smaller farms on the outskirts of Aarhus that provide food within the region. With over 20% of the consumers' food purchases being organic in Aarhus, there is quite a strong market for organic procurement compared to the average sale of organic products in Denmark. The gastronomy scene in Aarhus has also been established since 2000 with novel restaurants and street food markets, many of which have a focus on using local and seasonal produce, reinventing traditions, and employing the principles of New Nordic cuisine. Finally, Aarhus is still in the process of establishing an FPN as part of the FoodCLIC project.

The analysis of the planning frameworks, food policies and initiatives in Aarhus unveils a network of interconnected strategies spanning various scales, sectors, and institutional levels. These measures are crafted to enhance transformative (and green) shifts within food systems, with the overarching objective of promoting both human well-being, environmental sustainability, and local food economy.

Firstly, the **Planning Framework** – Municipality Plan (Kommuneplan) – approved by the City Council in 2019, sets out legislative conditions for the physical development in Aarhus city-region. The municipality plan is currently undergoing revision, as is required by national law. This entails public hearings and other measures to include relevant stakeholders in the planning process. This planning framework aims to create a sustainable environment that meets the needs of all people. In relation to the local food system, it takes into consideration land use planning and infrastructure which in turn impacts on food production and agricultural land availability. It also recognises the importance of achieving multiple sustainability co-benefits such as greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reduction through land use planning. The Municipality Plan also aims at *linking* the city with rural areas through green corridors that allow access to land and ensures the preservation of agricultural land and biodiversity. Furthermore, the Municipality Plan places a strong emphasis on citizen participation in the planning process through mechanisms such as Medborgerskab (policy for public involvement) and mandatory public consultations – i.e. a diverse spectrum of stakeholders are included in shaping the priorities and direction set by the Planning Framework.

At the **national level**, the Climate-Friendly Dietary Guidelines aim at promoting healthy and climate-friendly diets by encouraging people to eat more plant-rich and varied foods and to eat more whole grain products as well as reduce the intake of salt, sugar, and saturated fats. The guidelines suggest several pathways for achieving sustainability *co-benefits*, for example, through the promotion of climate-friendly diets that are culturally appropriate and accessible.

In relation to *inclusion*, the **national** policy “Regeringens strategi for mad, måltider og sundhed” (the Government’s Strategy for Food, Meals and Health) aims at achieving social, environmental, and economic goals while prioritizing the food habits of marginalised and vulnerable groups. Potential *co-benefits* of the strategy are focused on preventing dietary-related pathologies such as obesity through the promotion of healthier food choices and food education mainly in schools. Indeed, a central focus of the strategy lies in implementing interventions within schools to enhance children’s accessibility to nourishing meals. The strategy also aims to provide evidence-based information to consumers through easy labelling to avoid misinformation, especially of marginalised and vulnerable groups. The strategy also includes the creation of online databases (i.e. knowledge banks) that provide health and nutrition information to consumers and promote interventions with local associations such as NGOs and charities to reach marginalised and vulnerable groups. In terms of *connectivity*, innovation partnerships with the private sector are supported to develop healthier food products at more affordable prices.

Lastly, Aarhus is actively undertaking significant measures to attain carbon neutrality by the year 2030 currently through the **city-regional** Climate Action Plan 2021-2024, which is part of the Climate Strategy 2020-2030. The action plan’s key *co-benefit* is the reduction of CO₂ emissions by promoting sustainable practices and behaviour changes. The promoted practices include minimizing energy use by transitioning to fossil fuel-free production in agriculture, increasing the use of public

transportation and active modes of transportation such as biking and walking, and implementing a green food procurement strategy in public canteens including increased purchase of organic produce and an internal CO₂ tax on specific products like red meat. The goal of CO₂ emissions reduction drives additional *co-benefits*, including the conservation of biodiversity to mitigate carbon emissions and the establishment of public-private partnerships that enhance collaboration across sectors, promoting green growth, cultivating green transition skills, and advancing technology implementation. In terms of *inclusion*, the Climate Action Plan 2021-2024 aims to improve access to healthier and more affordable food options in urban areas by supporting local food production and green public procurement.

Initiatives

Of the 7 selected Aarhus initiatives, most have been established in the last 10 years, with only one starting earlier in 2004 – 4H Food School which was a replication of an initiative originally created in Canada. These initiatives were mainly initiated by highly educated groups or institutions such as universities. Yet, a few were developed by private businesses such as Coop – the second biggest retailer in Denmark. One of the main focuses of Aarhus initiatives is the *connection* between local farmers and the city's cafes, retail, restaurants and people, and the promotion of organic food. For instance, initiatives like coffee locales like the Mellemfolk Cafe or MoCa Cafe provide food produced mainly by small, local, and organic producers. While the former also acts as a meeting hub for farmers and civic organizations to share experiences and resources; the latter is a canteen that provides only vegetarian dishes and is committed to reducing food waste. On the other hand, Skraldecafeen (The Garbage Café) recovers food waste from local supermarkets to give it to marginalised and vulnerable groups, who, moreover, are directly involved in the cooking activities. The local grocery shop Raa Aarhus also facilitates the *connections* between local food producers, chefs, and consumers while fostering the use of organic ingredients, reduction of food packaging, and culinary innovation.

For these initiatives, the physical space is crucial for *linking* local farmers and other stakeholders and people. However, this may not always be necessary. The MoCa Cafe has also built relations with producers in other countries that are not physically close, such as an Italian cooperative that cultivates fruits following biodynamic agriculture's principles. The Instagram channel @derforlandmand also uses the internet as a platform to bring agriculture closer to young people. This novel approach shows the daily life of four chosen organic farmers between the ages of 18 and 25 to make it more appealing to young people to choose a life as a farmer. Another activity targeting the younger population, in this case children between 8 and 12 years old, is the 4H Food Schools. This initiative organises educational activities such as cooking classes, field trips and cultivating food in communal gardens during the summer. By doing so, it aims to give hands-on experience as well as knowledge about nature, food and animals.

This kind of punctual activities has also been used by other initiatives like the Mellemfolk Cafe which organises events and seminars to raise awareness on local cooperatives, the formation of CSAs (Community Supported Agriculture) and the agricultural landscape of Denmark. The retailer company Coop also raises awareness about the impacts of diets by suggesting dishes with a low environmental impact to its customers. The company has also developed a policy that aims at providing good, fair, and healthy food to their consumers by restricting the requirements for their suppliers concerning, for instance, the use of pesticides, energy consumption and packaging and transport.

3.2 AMSTERDAM

Table 3: Overview of Amsterdam Planning Frameworks, Policies and Initiatives

TYPE	TITLE	MAIN FOCUS	INITIATOR	TIME TIME FRAME	C L I C			
					C	L	I	C
National Food Policy	City Deal Healthy and Sustainable Food Environment	Food environments	Municipal-led, coordinated by National Government	2021-2025				
City-region food-related policy	Amsterdam Memorandum on Health policy	Health	Municipality	2021-2025				
Planning Framework	City district/ neighbourhood Hortus, part of the	Feeding the city, making it more healthy and green.	Municipality of Almere	Since 2023				

	Municipality of Almere							
Initiative	Voedseltuin IJplein (food garden IJplein)	Community garden to cultivate organic food, partly donated to the local food bank	Civil society	Since 2014				
Initiative	Farmers for Neighbours (Boeren voor Buren)	Giving farmers a fair price (for their surplus during Corona), whilst selling to various food initiatives (who help food deprived and vulnerable groups of people).	Two entrepreneurs	Since 2020				
Initiative	TommyToma to	School lunches at primary school for all kids (ensuring access to kids whose parents cannot afford it themselves).	Two entrepreneurs	Since 2020				
Initiative	Catering UvA/Hva	Providing local and healthy food for university canteens	A researcher and an employee from facility services (HvA/UvA)					
Initiative	Bloei & Groei (this translates to	Food garden targeting especially women of	Initiated by Ama Koranteng Kumi a	Since 2013				

	'Bloom & Grow')	colour with mental health issues	neighbourhood initiative					
Initiative	Boeren van Amstel	Farmers' association to foster sustainable agricultural practices and meadow bird conservation	A selection of 18 Farmers near Amsterdam	Since 2017				
Initiative	More than Milk Amsterdam	Shorten the supply chain between dairy producers and city	Marten Verdenius	Since 2013				

Food policies and planning framework

The Amsterdam Metropolitan Area is situated in a fertile agricultural production area. Yet the vast majority of the products consumed by its inhabitants are imported. In response, the municipality of Amsterdam has formulated the ambition to source 25% of the food consumed in the municipality from local sources by 2030. This aligns with the Netherlands' **national policy**, "City Deal Healthy and Sustainable Food Environment" which seeks to establish new rural-urban linkages, through the "City Deal policy plan". The aim of the City Deal is threefold: (i) to build more sustainable food environments, (ii) to encourage the adoption of healthy eating habits and (iii) to increase the consumption of *locally* produced food. The policy addresses food environments (physical and digital) as a leverage to improve environmental, social, and economic sustainability dimensions. At the same time, it addresses food-deprived and marginalised and vulnerable groups targeting food environments in vulnerable neighbourhoods as well as access and affordability of sustainable, healthy food for lower-income groups. This policy relies on a high level of cooperation between different governance levels and stakeholders who are also involved in the decision-making process to ensure cross-sectoral cooperation. Throughout the four-year commitment period, the City Deal aims to establish a learning community and an online platform where diverse food system actors can share and scale up innovations and lessons learned, working on concrete projects, guidelines, or policy frameworks to promote healthy and sustainable food environments. FPNs are envisioned to have a crucial role in aligning food system transformation with context-dependent concerns like climate change, resource scarcity, and biodiversity conservation. Indeed, three FPNs are operating

in the city-region: 'Stichting Voedsel Verbindt' ("food connects") which serves as a network for higher education institutes, policymakers and the private sectors, 'Haarlem Food Future' that *connects* people-oriented initiatives, start-ups and food cooperatives and the 'Food Council Metropolitan Region Amsterdam' which is involved in various food initiatives, research projects and really functions as a food network hub.

The **city-regional** Amsterdam Memorandum on Health policy was issued by the Mayor and Aldermen of Amsterdam with the purpose of improving the health of people in three city districts: Amsterdam Noord, Zuidoost and Nieuw-West. The policy is foreseen to last from 2021 to 2025 and addresses specifically the young population and marginalised and vulnerable groups by increasing their food literacy and access to healthy and affordable food. For instance, access to healthy food for low-income groups is addressed through food banks and short food supply chain initiatives to improve access to healthy food at a lower price. Other action lines focus on increasing the price of unhealthy food and decreasing the prices of healthy food via lobbying and improving the healthiness of food environments, in synergy with the "City Deal Healthy and Sustainable Food Environment".

The **planning framework** "city district/neighbourhood Hortus", part of the municipality of Almere, can be considered as a Living Lab where innovations for green and healthy cities are tested. Thus, the interventions should be replicable and scalable and are designed across four key themes of intervention: (i) Feeding the City: integrating food production in and around the city (ii) Greening the City: 'green' as a crucial part of a 'liveable' city (iii) Energizing the City: closed cycles, using the environment for energy, self-supplying systems and energy production (iv) Healthying the City: striving for the general welfare, social cohesion, healthy food and novel care concepts. Particular emphasis is given to "food-related issues" such as health, obesity, children's access to food, employment and affordability of living in the city. In this regard, the municipality of Almere is pursuing an integrated approach by working on health, food, and sustainability conjointly. The "city district/neighbourhood Hortus" focuses its attention on an urban context, but also tries to raise awareness toward local food production among urban dwellers for instance through local food markets and urban gardens open to school children and residents. The willingness to increase *inclusivity* is also part of this planning framework, specifically toward low-income groups and people with limited mobility. The cooperation with the local University of Applied Sciences (Flevo Campus) has helped to carry out studies about urban gardening. Furthermore, in the neighbourhood, there is a centre called Food Forum which plays an important role in the food heritage of the neighbourhood and research on food topics in general all throughout the AMA.

Initiatives

Of the seven initiatives in Amsterdam focused on in this report, three were initiated by civil society organisations and four by private individuals. Three were founded 10 years ago, and the other three around 2020. The initiatives focus on two main topics: (1) the creation of urban gardens for people,

and in particular marginalised people, to cultivate their own food and, (2) the shortening of the supply chains between producers in the rural areas surrounding the city and the urban consumers.

Initiatives like the IJplein food garden (Voedseltuin IJplein) and the Bloei & Groei (“Bloom & Grow”) were both initiated by civil society organizations and are examples of providing access to land and food growing for marginalised and vulnerable groups. Voedseltuin IJplein focuses on the low-income neighbourhood where it is located. Bloei & Groei is a food garden involving women of colour, and in particular those with mental health issues. Voedseltuin IJplein cultivates food mainly for donating purposes, as 75% goes towards the food banks and 25% is for self-consumption. This initiative also promotes education on food and environment in schools, whereas Bloei & Groei is less focused on the actual production of food and more on the contribution to the city's biodiversity by promoting sustainable cultivation practices.

Boeren van Amstel is also an initiative that supports sustainable agriculture, by encouraging dairy farmers of the rural Amstelland region to diminish the use of pesticides and fertilizers and fostering conservation efforts to maintain an adequate habitat for meadow birds. These conservation efforts are then rewarded through a commission on each pack of milk sold in the city. Boeren Van Amstel works in close collaboration with the Meadow Bird Fund to realise this economic model. Like Boeren van Amstel, other initiatives also aim at connecting urban dwellers to the rural areas. More than Milk Amsterdam (MOMA), for instance, connects dairy producers from the surrounding rural area to the city and thus shortening the food chain. Farmers for Neighbours (Boeren voor Buren) is another example that focuses on providing high-quality, fresh and affordable food to marginalised and vulnerable groups while also reducing food waste.

Another initiative, Tommy Tomato, works on shortening food chains by connecting rural farmers with primary school canteens in order to create more ‘vegetable eating moments’ throughout the day. The initiative promotes plant-based diets, provides educational materials and organises educational programming for children about food. For example, as part of Tommy Tomato’s programme, the SoeperChef cooking lessons help develop children's skills and knowledge about vegetables, healthy nutrition and the local food system, another programme "Health Angels' ' provides opportunities for senior people to share their knowledge and deliver lunches to children. Another knowledge exchange initiative in the city-region, Catering HvA/UvA has set up a community of practice consisting of various university educational departments such as dietary, logistics and environment with the goal to formulate a food vision for the higher education institutions which should translate directly to its own catering and banqueting policy. Regarding the *connectivities* that have been set up by the initiatives with other sectors, Boeren voor Buren collaborates both with public and private institutions (such as the Flevopolder region, and Studiezalen Foundation, Rabobank, Flevofood) to leverage their expertise, networks, and resources and to reach more customers. MOMA engages city dwellers through the program “soil alliance” which allows people to participate in soil-restoring programmes

and Boeren van Amstel has spaces dedicated to host visitors and inform them on local agricultural practices and wildlife conservation efforts, also as a way of *linking* urban dwellers to the rural area.

3.3 BARCELONA

Table 4: Overview of Barcelona Planning Frameworks, Policies and Initiatives

TYPE	TITLE	MAIN FOCUS	INITIATOR	TIME TIME FRAME	C L I C			
					C	L	I	C
National Food Policy Autonomous government	PEAC – Strategic Food Plan of Catalonia 2021 - 2026	Sustainable and competitive food systems	State (Catalonia)	2021-2026				
City-regional Food Policy	"Escoles + Sostenibles" (Schools + Sustainable)	"Feed yourself wisely" (Training of trainers for teachers). Prevention and loss of food waste	Municipality	2020				
City-regional food policy	Special plan for the protection and improvement of the Baix Llobregat Agricultural Park (2003) Review of the Special Plan (2015)	Restriction of urbanization and promotion of sustainable agriculture	Metropolitan Government	2003-2015				

Initiative	Banc de Terres	Recovering abandoned land	Territorial Agricultural Directorate of the Technical Office for Municipal Prevention of Forest Fires and Agricultural Development of the Diputació de Barcelona	2019				
Initiative	Terra Pagesa	Platform to connect farmers and public and private buyers	Unió de Pagesos	2021				
Initiative	La Botiga del Prat	Provide food that is about to expire to vulnerable people, with preference for organic, local and seasonal products	Cáritas organisation, Prat de Llobregat Red Cross	2019-2024				
Initiative	Xamec	Promotes the agroecological transition in school canteens	Network process among 5 agroecologic canteen management companies	2017				
Initiative	Agròpolis	Advocacy for agroecology and food sovereignty	Barcelona city council	2019				
Initiative	Fundació Espigoladors	Reduction of food waste, gleaning, food	3 individuals	2014				

		redistribution and employment for vulnerable people						
Initiative	Alterbanc	Provide access to sustainable and healthy food to vulnerable people	EcoCentral, an agroecological distributor, with the support of agroecological entities and neighborhood networks.	2020				

Food policies and planning framework

The designation of Barcelona as the World Capital of Sustainable Food in 2021 has spurred the adoption of **city-regional** food strategies by several cities in the metropolitan region. Barcelona’s agri-food industry is thriving, supported by a well-developed distribution network that includes Barcelona’s Port and Mercabarna, renowned for food imports, exports, and local food branding. With a total population of 3.3 million residing in a compact 636 km² area, the city-region plays a pivotal role in shaping food systems. Municipal markets play a vital role in providing access to fresh produce, while community-based and informal food organizations contribute to minimizing food waste, promoting circular economies, and enhancing social cohesion. Moreover, gastronomy plays a significant role in the city-region’s cultural heritage, offering a wide array of traditional and place-based restaurants. Associations across the food chain, as well as public administrations actively participate in the agri-food sector. For example, the City’s Coordination Office for Sustainable Food aims to enhance inter-departmental and sectoral collaboration. Moreover, the city-region acknowledges the necessity for enhancing public health due to the increasing prevalence of food-related diseases. To address this and other food-related issues, three interrelated policies have been enacted.

The Special Plan for the Protection and Improvement of the Baix Llobregat Agricultural Park aims at safeguarding and enhancing the agricultural park in the Baix Llobregat region near Barcelona. The park covers an area of approximately 3,000 hectares in the delta and lower valley of the Llobregat River. The Special Plan, which works as an urban planning tool, safeguards the natural and agricultural landscape by implementing regulations and measures that restrict urbanization within its territory, while maintaining a balance between agricultural, ecological, and social functions. For example, the Special Plan has curtailed urban pressure on the fluvial and agricultural areas by prohibiting the development on its natural resources, unless it is development related to sustainable

agricultural activities. The plan facilitates a range of *co-benefits* by effectively balancing the preservation of natural areas with the development of urban spaces within the metropolitan area, while also revitalizing agricultural sites. Furthermore, the promotion of ecological *connectivity* in the Agricultural Park, with a focus on cardio-healthy routes and recreational orchards, particularly benefiting the elderly, creates public health *co-benefits*. The governing body of the Baix Llobregat Agricultural Park known as Park Consortium facilitates participatory round table dialogues to improve collaboration between farmers, associations, and local authorities and to increase agricultural knowledge and support self-employed workers to access land. Hence, the park serves as a catalyst for fostering a deeper connection and recognition of the cultural and historical significance of farming practices and communities. The Special Plan for the Protection and Improvement of the Baix Llobregat Agricultural Park is also concerned with the issues of *inclusive* access to fair land management by including marginalized farmers (i.e young farmers and farm workers who are not landowners) in the management and use of the park.

The objectives of the Special Plan are synergistically reinforced by the **national-level** PEAC – Strategic Food Plan of Catalonia 2021-2026. The PEAC aims to create a sustainable and competitive food system that produces healthy and high-quality foods, and it is rooted in the diversity of agri-food systems in Catalonia. PEAC has been developed as a result of a participatory process involving 37 stakeholders. Its purpose is to provide guidance for public policies across various departments of the Catalan government. The PEAC encompasses a range of *co-benefits*. Firstly, circularity in agri-food practices is emphasised, including food waste reduction and recycling, the importance of the bioeconomy sector, and renewable energies in the agri-food and fishing sectors. The promotion of responsible and sustainable production and consumption practices amongst producers by giving priority to environmentally friendly production methods is also encouraged. Moreover, the PEAC Plan fosters collaboration with associations to promote agricultural heritage. In terms of *linkages*, the plan aims at re-establishing connections between urban and rural areas by diversifying local agri-food production through diverse production methods, improving conditions for professionals entering the agricultural and fishing sectors through vocational training and especially integrating women into rural and maritime activities. Furthermore, *inclusion* is the key aspect of the PEAC, with a focus on guaranteeing all people, and especially marginalised and vulnerable groups, access to decent food and fair work conditions in the agri-food sector.

The aforementioned policies are reinforced by the initiatives of the participatory network "Barcelona + Sostenible," which encompasses over 1,900 organizations committed to environmental, social, and economic sustainability. The main objective of the network is to incorporate sustainability principles into educational institutions and learning curricula, enhancing environmental awareness amongst the youngest consumers and fostering meaningful *connections* between health, education and food. It emphasises environmental education through learning sustainable practices such as waste reduction and energy efficiency measures and promotes sustainable mobility practices. Finally, Barcelona + Sostenible emphasises the consumption of healthy, locally sourced food, aiming at

improving the livelihoods of agricultural communities in the region. Educational and cultural change is also emphasised with regard to training, resource-sharing, and community involvement in capacity-building. In terms of *linkages*, the focus is placed on environmental education and close collaborations with schools to re-establish *connections* between nature and children – for example, by incorporating green spaces and environmental education into the school curriculum and establishing the Network of Schools for the Sustainability of Catalonia.

Initiatives

Barcelona witnessed the establishment of many food-related initiatives in the last few years, founded by both locally-run institutions and civil society organizations. Initiatives are strongly focused on empowering local farmers and promoting their products in the urban area, while fostering sustainable practices such as agroecology. Banc de Terres, for instance, aims to identify and recover abandoned or unused land and help the transfer to whoever is interested in making it productive again. It prioritises young farmers and offers both an online platform (Bancdeterres.cat) where the young farmers, landowners and future buyers can access relevant information, and legal advice to set up the contracts and practical advice to recover the fields.

There are other initiatives that work to facilitate the sale of local products inside the city area and to foster the recovery of food waste. For example, Terra Pagesa is a local food distribution centre that *connects* farmers to markets and canteen management companies, improving remuneration conditions for producers and promoting access to local and seasonal products for people. Regarding food waste, Fundació Espigoladors and La Botiga del Prat aim to recover food that would otherwise be wasted. The former saves food from the fields that cannot be sold due to aesthetic reasons, sets the prices together with the farmers so that their costs of production are always covered and sells both the raw products and the processed ones (such as marmalades, creams or patés) at affordable prices for vulnerable and food-deprived communities. La Botiga del Prat also recovers discarded food with preference for local, organic, and seasonal food, and makes it available to the vulnerable people in El Prat de Llobregat. Both initiatives also have an educational focus through education and training for farmers (especially on agroecological practices and fair-trade practices) or the creation of spaces for sharing and communicating with disadvantaged people to find job opportunities, respectively.

The initiative Cuchara also aims at fostering food education to help people make informed choices and promote especially consumption of seasonal, locally produced food. To this end, Cuchara provides collective cooking spaces and classes on how to make recipes with food waste that contribute to generating debates and reflections around food consumption. Espai participatiu Agròpolis also focuses on raising awareness around the benefits of short circuits and fostering knowledge exchange and mutual support between rural and urban communities. This initiative also aims at influencing public policies and developing autonomous agri-food systems in urban and peri-

urban areas coordinated through collective social action. Creating local agri-food chains is also at the centre of Xamec (Xarxa agroecològica de Menjadors Escolars de Catalunya). Xamec promotes the uptake of food grown through agroecological practices in canteens and provides training to families and teachers about agroecological practices, advocates for responsible public procurement and boosts networking with other companies to improve transparency in the catering for schools.

3.4 BERLIN

Table 5: Overview of Berlin Planning Frameworks, Policies and Initiatives

TYPE	TITLE	MAIN FOCUS	INITIATOR	TIME TIME FRAME	C L I C			
					C	L	I	C
National Food policy	German Food and Nutrition Strategy	Healthy environment for food and movement	The Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL)	In progress -due end 2023				
City-region Food Policy	Berlin food strategy (Ernährungsstrategie)	Sustainable food system in the city-region	Local Government-led (Senate)	Since 2020				
City-region Food Policy	Law on the quality improvement of school lunches	School meals	Berlin parliament	Since 2003				

Planning Framework	Neighbourhood management program (Quartiersmanagement Berlin)	Improving social cohesion and living conditions	Local government (Senate) department for Urban development	Since 1990			
Initiatives	Netzwerk der Lebensmittel Punkte (LMPs)	Neighborhood food hubs for community cooking and food democracy	Civil society	Since 2020			
Initiatives	Kantine Zukunft (AH)	Consultant to improve quality and sustainability of institutional food	Service provider "Speiseräume GmbH"	Since 2019			
Initiatives	Ernährungsrat Berlin e.V. + equivalent food council in Brandenburg	Advocacy and collective action for better and fairer regional food system	Civil society	Since 2016			
Initiatives	Restlos Glücklich e.V.	Educational workshops on food waste and climate-friendly nutrition	Civil society	Since 2014			
Initiatives	Yeşil Çember gGmbH	Awareness and community empowerment to promote sustainable	Civil society/Service Provider	Since 2012			

		lifestyles, particularly among Turkish and Arabic-speaking groups						
Initiatives	Foodsharing e.V.	Online platform for food sharing	Civil society	Since 2012				
Initiatives	Hilfelotse Berlin	Web platform to search for health and social support services	Ministry of Health, District of Reinickendorf in Berlin, and service partner Albatros gGmbH	Since 1984 (Albatros gGmbH)				
Initiatives	Über den Tellerrand (AH)	Communal kitchen and mentoring to foster exchange between Berliners with and without refugee experiences	Bontu Guschke (idea) & Carolin Strehmel (both FU students), Ninon Demut & Gerrit Küschner (TU)	Since 2013				
Initiatives	Die Tafel mit Laib und Seele (e.V.)	Redistribution of fresh food, volunteers, and employees from social assistance-receiving groups	Sabine Werth	Since 1993				
Initiatives	PEP - platform for food and	Joint cooking classes with young people and seniors, to	Service provider; run by symbioun e.V. and official partner of the	Since 2020				

	movement gGmbH	promote healthy lifestyle	Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL)					
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Food policies and planning framework

The Berlin city-region has a multicultural population and hosts 500,000 daily visitors. The food system in the region boasts one of Europe's largest consumer markets for organic food, however, access to healthy and sustainable food for disadvantaged groups is a concern. Indeed, according to Eurostat data (2022), a total of 22 % of Germany's lower-income population cannot afford a wholesome meal every other day. The city-region's goals focus on empowering communities affected by food poverty and allowing them to participate in and shape the food environment they live in.

The city signed the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact in 2015 which resulted in the development of the **city-regional** "Berlin Food Strategy". This strategy aims to create a sustainable city-region food system focusing on seven key areas: collective catering, regional supply chains, innovation, lively neighbourhoods, nutritional education, food waste, and administration as a food sustainability example. Improving access to healthy and quality food is central to the strategy, with an added focus on vulnerable and marginalised groups such as the elderly and youth. For instance, the strategy aligns with a prior law to provide school meals for children from grades 1 to 6 free of charge and support for parents on social income for the costs of kindergarten meals. Furthermore, a training and transitioning programme for public canteens was launched in 2019 with the goal of transforming more than 4 million canteen plates per year; thus far, over 40 kitchens are transitioning to a minimum share of 60% organic and seasonal produce from the region. The strategy also contributes to creating an overarching platform for potential *connections* and networks across sectors, for example pursuing research on youth food environments, foodsharing start-ups and food waste initiatives within neighbourhoods.

In 2003, the City State of Berlin pioneered a law on the quality criteria for school meals in the city. This law aims to improve the nutritional values and quality of school meals in line with the national guidelines in the 'German Food and Nutrition Strategy' as well as to create uniform tender procedures with a monitoring system. The law was updated in 2019 with the goal of increasing to 50% the share of organic food served in school meals by 2022 and providing school meals free of charge to primary school children from grades 1 to 6. The 2019 reform was influenced by parents' associations and their call for a stronger guarantee of nutritious school meals to all school children.

At a **national level**, the German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture is in the process of developing a comprehensive Food and Nutrition strategy to improve food environments for better health outcomes and increased movement and exercise of all people, with a plan to develop concrete measures and indicators. The strategy will become effective in 2023 and build on existing action plans. According to the Ministry, it has adopted a bottom-up participatory method to develop the strategy, organising workshops and public consultation. However, participating stakeholders have challenged the level of transparency in strategy development, limited by a disorganised and at times ad hoc process lacking in prioritization.

In 1990, the German Ministry of Interior, launched a federal Neighbourhood Management Program (Quartiers management) aimed at improving the living conditions of residents after reunification. For the purpose of this report, this program is considered a **planning framework**, because it targets the neighbourhood scale. This programme was updated in 2022 with the goal of initiating sustainable, long-lasting urban development processes in 33 Berlin neighbourhoods by focusing on three integrated areas: Education, Public Space and Social and Ethnic integration. Regarding environmental aspects, the measures focus on climate protection and adaptation in the form of social projects, for example, working with the Edible Cities Network European project to develop public edible resources such as urban gardens in the neighbourhood. As part of this Neighbourhood Management Program, local people councils follow a participatory model for budgeting, leadership, and network building. The project selection relies on the preferences of neighbourhood councils which often prioritise social issues (e.g., crime or childcare). Indeed, social cohesion is high on the agenda compared to other topics with a focus on community events, workshops, and skills development training. The implementation on the ground is carried out by self-organized collective local stakeholders including urban gardeners, schoolteachers and parent associations, health, youth and community centres, and coordinated through the district project teams as well as the respective district offices and the senate administrations. In terms of achievements, the Neighbourhood Management Program has worked with 1,300 people in their neighbourhood councils and between 1999 and 2019 has distributed over €472M in participatory budgeting towards community self-organised social integration and cohesion efforts, including urban gardens.

Initiatives

Berlin has a mature food network, energised by many civil society organizations, organic and Community Supported Agriculture (CSA) market players and a growing number of organisations that implement projects funded under the Berlin food strategy (as service providers). Among those analysed in this report, the first initiative was launched in 1983 while the most recent started in 2020. These initiatives are strongly focused on strengthening local community building, advocacy and awareness around food challenges and solutions and enabling both the current and future generations to have a voice and impact on food-related issues.

Most food initiatives and organisations in Berlin focus specifically on awareness raising and training directed towards different target groups. For instance, Kantine Zukunft trains the staff of canteen kitchens to provide more healthy and sustainable food by using seasonal and regional products. Restlos Glücklich is another example that focuses on raising awareness on food waste and climate-friendly nutrition by organizing educational workshops for both children and adults and they also provide a web platform for anyone to share their food-saving recipes and tips. Similarly, PEP – platform for food and movement – offers collaborative cooking workshops where people can share healthy recipes and cook together to increase nutritional competence and healthy lifestyle skills. They focus especially on children and elders and the cross-generational exchange that emerges. Finally, the Netzwerk der LebensMittelPunkte (LMPs) creates neighbourhood places to collect and distribute food, as well as cook together and exchange knowledge in community food systems. Products are supplied via CSAs or local farmers from Brandenburg. This contributes to raising awareness on how small businesses in the local agricultural sector work, their needs and capacities and enables innovative support systems in urban markets. From these activities, a stronger sense of community is built with food and the future of the city-region as a common thread.

Other initiatives focus on food redistribution such as Foodsharing.de which is an online platform that allows users to find food nearby that they can take for free and without the need to be referred. People can also become ambassadors to promote and coordinate food-sharing services in their neighbourhoods. Hilfelotse Berlin is another online platform that, among other things, provides concrete information on food banks, price-friendly canteens, cafeterias and non-profit meal delivery services - especially for people living with physical and/or socio-economic barriers. Finally, Die Tafel mit Laib und Seele comprises 400 institutions re-distributing fresh produce and bread products for a nominal fee. This is part of the national network of food-aid centres in Germany, but with its own membership base and political advocacy for the needs and services of Berlin's food insecure. Volunteers and employees, coming mostly from social assistance-receiving groups, run and operate the food services and outreach programs.

Another cluster of initiatives focuses on Berlin's rich migrant communities. Yeşil Çember, for instance, hosts cooking workshops and intercultural events, provides educational material and training, and launches campaigns to increase dialogue on sustainable lifestyles among Turkish and Arabic-speaking groups. Another example is the case of Über den Tellerrand, a program created around the concept of a welcome kitchen for refugees. It contributes to skill sharing and integration between people with refugee and non-refugee backgrounds. The kitchen is seen as a vehicle to promote community building through cooking and shared activities.

Finally, to bring people's demands in the political arena, Ernährungsrat Berlin e.V. (food council) convenes people and civil society organisations to create solutions and demand political support for the food transition. The Ernährungsrat supports the development of LMPs, works to create a food transition campus and mobilises inhabitants to demand fair access to food, reconnecting producers

and consumers and creating *inclusive* food environments for diverse and underrepresented communities.

3.5 BRASOV

Table 6: Overview of Brasov Planning Frameworks, Policies and Initiatives

TYPE	TITLE	MAIN FOCUS	INITIATOR	TIME TIME FRAME	C L I C			
					C	L	I	C
National Food Policy	Education for healthy life for Romanian children	Food education, healthy eating	State-led	2017-2023				
City-region food policy	Children education for healthy food and delivery of healthy food to school: The Integrated Development Strategy of the Brasov Metropolitan Area - Strategic objective 2	Food education, healthy eating, local food production	Municipality-led	2020-2030				
City-region food policy	Public Markets Administration Service Braşov - Decision of Local Council no. 428/09.07.2022	Local food products and local food economy	Municipality led	2020-2030				

Planning Framework	Flywheel markets	Local food products and local economy	Municipality - led					
Initiative	Meal civilization in Braşov	Promote and recover the food intangible heritage of the old Brasov community	Administration of the National Cultural Fund (AFCN)	2020				
Initiative	Arena Chefs, Out of Passion for PEOPLE	Food donation to families in need	National Association of Chefs and Confectioners in Tourism	2020-2030				
Initiative	Food Bank Braşov	Collect food donation and distribute them to NGO with social purposes	Food Bank Brasov NGO	2020-2030				
Initiative	Arrangement of energy production park from renewable sources for commercialization at the UAT level	Park for energy production from renewable sources for commercialization		2020-2030				
Initiative	Doripesco	Valorisation of fishery products	Doripesco Group	1995				
Initiative	The Fair of Brasov Producers	Promotion of local traditional food in the local fair	Brasov Municipality	2022-2025				

Initiative	The Innkeepers' Guild from Braşov	Increasing the demand for high-quality meals in restaurants	the for in	The Innkeepers' Guild NGO	2018				
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Food policies and planning framework

The Brasov city-region, situated in the picturesque Romanian Carpathian Mountains, boasts a longstanding heritage in the agri-food and beverage industry, specializing in the production of dairy, meat, confectionery, beer, and natural products (such as wild honey, forest fruits and wild edible mushrooms). Despite this, Romania's heavy dependence on food imports and the prevalence of obesity constitute significant challenges. To address these and further challenges, the city-region of Brasov has been implementing a set of comprehensive policies and planning frameworks that specifically focus on enhancing local food production, promoting food culture, and prioritizing education.

For example, the Brasov Municipality has introduced a **planning framework** called Flywheel Markets, which aims to establish markets in the form of producers' fairs within the Brasov Municipality region. These markets serve as platforms to showcase and promote agricultural producers and agri-food companies with sales outlets in the agri-food markets of Brasov. The Flywheel Markets bring several *co-benefits* by prioritizing improvements in public health and nutrition by increasing access to local and high-quality fresh food. Additionally, it encourages the active participation of farmers in the organization of the markets and promotes specifically the participation of organic accredited farmers which promotes transparency of local food supply chains through organic or mountain product labelling. Finally, the planning framework strengthens urban-rural *linkages* by connecting farmers in rural areas with consumers in the city.

The productive *linkages* mentioned above are strengthened through the implementation of the **national-level** "Education for Healthy Life for Romanian Children" program in schools throughout Romania. This program has the objective of promoting healthy eating habits, providing food education, and financing access to nutritious food, especially fresh fruits, vegetables, and milk. The program produces various *co-benefits*, with a significant focus on improving public health by implementing enhanced nutrition practices in the schools' curricula. It also contributes to an increase in demand for locally produced agri-food products and serves as a catalyst for the growth of organic farms and the adoption of eco-certifications. It is important to stress that the implementation of the program strongly relies on the active participation of certified organic farmers who also value traditional and regional agricultural products. This approach seeks to encourage the

growth of attractive production-type employment opportunities in rural regions and reduce the out-migration of jobs from rural areas. By strengthening the *linkages* and building *connections* between various political stakeholders and producers, the program establishes connections at different scales, sectors and institutional levels.

The objectives of this program are further strengthened and scaled up by a **city-regional** policy, namely "The Integrated Development Strategy of the Brasov Metropolitan Area, Strategic objective 2 – Innovation, entrepreneurship, and human capital: Attracting companies in ZMB and supporting the development of existing ones towards areas of specialization intelligence and innovation, 2.2.2. Supporting local producers." This policy aims to foster integrated development in the city-region and enhance local food systems in the Brasov Metropolitan Area through the promotion of innovation, entrepreneurship, and human capital. The policy aims not only at improving the overall health of the population, but also to support and promote local farmers. To achieve its objectives, the policy establishes *linkages* between rural farmers and urban schools, ensuring the delivery of healthy food to educational institutions and knowledge sharing. The policy adopts an *inclusive* approach by targeting the needs of low-income pensioners, single-parent families, students, and small-scale farmers. The policy *connects* rural and urban areas with various policy institutions and brings farmers and consumers together by building mutual trust and transparency in the food supply chain.

Finally, the "Public Markets Administration Service Braşov - Decision of Local Council no. 428/09.07.2022" policy focuses on the administration of public markets within the Braşov region, aiming to enhance the efficiency, accessibility, and sustainability of these markets. This **city-regional** policy puts in place a regulatory framework for supporting small-scale farmers and preserving the region's agricultural heritage. The policy increases the participation of local farmers in urban markets, making local and seasonal food accessible to all inhabitants and ensuring the availability of fresh, locally sourced products on a daily basis. This facilitates the *link* between producers and urban dwellers – as well as schools – which builds trust and contributes to the financial stability of small-scale farmers. Moreover, the policy prioritises marginalised and vulnerable groups like low-income pensioners, single-parent families, and students to ensure their access to nutritious and affordable food options, thereby addressing social inequalities and improving food security in the Brasov city-region.

Initiatives

Brasov initiatives are very recent, almost all of them started in 2020 or after, except for one issued by the Doripesco group in 1995. They were founded either by local institutions or by NGOs and local associations. Many of these initiatives are promoting local food traditions that are being lost, especially among the young population. The first initiative is "Meal civilization in Braşov" whose goal is to recover and spread the food heritage of the old Brasov community. In particular, it aims to involve young people through video materials and tasting sessions. A similar approach can be

observed at the Fair of Brasov Producers where traditional and locally-produced food products are sold. The initiative helps both to raise awareness among the population about adequate nutrition and to economically support local farmers. Another initiative promoting local food products is the association “The Innkeepers’ Guild from Braşov” which targets mainly tourists. The members, such as restaurants and cafes, buy products from nearby farmers who have no direct access to the city’s supermarkets. Similarly, Doripesco focuses on the promotion of fishery products coming from wild and domestic lakes in the Braşov city-region. The fish is then sold in both markets and supermarkets in Braşov. Moreover, the fishing and processing techniques used have a low environmental impact, making it a sustainable economic activity.

The last two initiatives focus on food donation. The first, “Arena Chefs, Out of Passion for PEOPLE”, is donating 2,000 meals prepared by 12 renowned chefs to families in need in Braşov county, with the participation of the supermarkets that provide the food. The second, “Food Bank Braşov”, collects food donations and redistributes them to NGOs working in the social sector. The final recipients are the deprived residents of the counties of Braşov, Mureş, Harghita, and Covasna. Finally, although not directly related to food, the Brasov municipality created an initiative to produce electricity from renewable sources which is then used for food preparation, among other purposes.

3.6 BUDAPEST

Table 7: Overview of Budapest Planning Frameworks, Policies and Initiatives

TYPE	TITLE	MAIN FOCUS	INITIATOR	TIME TIME FRAME	C L I C			
					C	L	I	C
National food policy	Freely accessible web-based registry of small-scale farmers and food produced by small-scale farmers.	Protecting small-scale farmers, including organic producers	Hungarian Chamber of Agriculture	Since 2020				
National food policy	Government Decree 676/2020 (XII.	Sustainable public food procurement	Government decree	Since 2022				

	28.) on special rules for public procurement procedures for public catering							
City-region food-related policy	2030 Long-term Urban Development Concept	Green spaces	Municipality-led	2013-2030				
National food policy	Government Decree 676/2020 (XII. 28.) on special rules for public procurement procedures for public catering	Sustainable public food procurement	Government decree	Since 2022				
Planning framework	Call for tenders for agricultural leasehold properties	Land lease for horticultural purposes	Municipality-led	Since 2008				
Initiative	Auróra Klímakert és közösségi komposztáló (Auróra Climate garden and community composter)	Composting, growing trees	Mark Richards and his friends, so called "Compost Community")	2018				
Initiative	Budapest Bike Maffia – Make plus one sandwich (aka +1 sandwich Project)	Provide a sandwich to food insecure people	Budapest Bike Maffia (CSO)	2011				

Initiative	Food strategy for the 19th districts	Provide locally and sustainably grown food	Transition Community of Wekerle (CSO)	2017				
Initiative	Heroes of Responsible Dining	Raise awareness on sustainable and organic farming, promote small farmers, advisory to caterings, certification activities	4 people, now evolved in an NGO	2012				
Initiative	Munch	Platform to sell at a discounted price the unsold food	Munch Europe Kft.	2020				
Initiative	'Te meg Én' tanoda ("You and me" after-school tutoring program)	Provide food to disadvantaged children and prevent food waste	TE+ÉN reformed christian community	2014				
Initiative	Heti betevő // Weekly food	Food provision to marginalised people	Employees of the restaurant Kisüzem	2013				

Food policies and planning framework

The Budapest city-region is committed to implementing an *inclusive*, resilient, diverse, and sustainable food system focusing on strengthening rural-urban *linkages* and short food supply chains. To achieve those objectives, various stakeholders are committed (i) to innovate and improve existing social justice-oriented food initiatives; thereby increasing the access to healthy and sustainable diets for the most vulnerable groups; (ii) to develop a more climate-resilient food system; (iii) to increase the proportion of healthy and locally sourced food offered in public schools and on markets.

In 2020, the Hungarian Chamber of Agriculture issued a **national law** to protect local small-scale farmers. This law is in place all over Hungary, but it is particularly relevant in the Budapest city-region. In Hungary, small-scale farmers belong to a legal category and own a special license to sell their products on the food markets under favourable tax conditions. However, they suffer from unfair competition from “pseudo farmers” who own a small plot of land where they do not grow food but sell low-quality and cheaper food bought from wholesale markets. In doing so, these “pseudo farmers” deceive the legal system to receive the same benefits as real small-scale producers which damages the business and reputation of the latter. The phenomenon was so widespread that in some farmers’ markets in Budapest, the rate of ‘pseudo-farmers’ was over two-thirds. To face this issue, the new legislation aims to create an open online dataset where all real small-scale farmers are registered and all consumers can check where the food they are buying comes from by scanning a QR code, using an app or a web page.

Another measure aimed at promoting short food supply chains is the “Government Decree 676/2020 (XII. 28.) on special rules for public procurement procedures for public catering”, which is a **national policy** aimed at improving the sustainability and quality of food supplied by collective catering in public canteens. To achieve this goal, the Decree establishes evaluation criteria for the selection of public catering which go beyond the lowest price criterion. According to the Decree, collective catering must purchase 80% – until 2023, 60% – of the raw materials from local food producers and short supply chains. To this purpose, the Decree provides the definitions of local food products and catering short supply chains. The former is defined as labelled products by the procedure (e.g., designations of origin) or legislated on the conditions of production and sale of food by small producers. Short supply chains cannot have more than one intermediate actor between the primary producer or food business operator and the catering operator. As part of the Decree, additional award criteria concern the use of a higher proportion of products from short supply chains or local food products compared to the mandatory share, consideration of consumer feedback, provision of more fruit and vegetables than required, transportation time between preparation and serving, and the share of organic food supplied.

The Municipality of the 11th district also aims at promoting urban agriculture as a means to increase food access, food education and community building through a “call for tenders for agricultural leasehold properties”. Through this **policy framework** people can apply for land leases for horticultural purposes with the aim to preserve “a wonderful oasis in the heart of Budapest.” The rent is low (0,21 euros/m²) and the size of the gardens makes them suitable for families. Applications are selected by the Municipality, prioritizing people without gardens and to families with several children to reduce the household cost of living. City inhabitants who obtain the land are committed to organic and agroecology gardening and they use the compost to improve the soil's physical, chemical, and biological properties. There is no control system, however, there is a group of people who try to spread the importance of agroecological principles among the gardeners. Educational activities with children and adults are organised by the people who rent the land. Regarding water

provision, a Water Association has been created to guarantee a common water supply system and new gardeners can join the association.

Progresses in the same direction have been made with the "2030 Long-term Urban Development Concept" by the Municipality of Budapest. This **city-regional** policy relies on three cross-cutting goals: liveability, sustainability, and equal opportunities. The policy aims to raise awareness about sustainability among city inhabitants and to increase and improve the green spaces of the city in order to design healthy urban environments. Green spaces are intended to include land to grow food with agroecological practices to develop urban agriculture and community gardens. Besides, the policy aims to support small-scale farming and agroecological practices.

Initiatives

In Budapest, there are mainly grassroots initiatives that function as drivers for change and most of them were initiated around 10 years ago. They are strongly focused on food provision for marginalised and vulnerable groups. For instance, "Weekly food" provides meals every Sunday to 2,000 food-deprived people and offers exclusively food with low environmental impact. Moreover, it provides information about the ingredients and where they come from. This initiative works not only in the capital but also in the rural areas and combines food provision with clothing and book distribution and back-to-school support. Another example is "Te meg Én' tanoda" program, which focuses specifically on children from disadvantaged families of Roma ethnic origin. The initiative offers school tutoring and, in cooperation with local supermarkets, provides meals to children, contributing to reducing food waste as supermarkets offer food that is close to the expiry date.

"Budapest Bike Maffia – Make plus one sandwich" also works with children but, in this case, children – together with their parents and teachers – prepare an extra sandwich - on top of the one for themselves – that is brought by bike to social shelters. Each school year, this initiative provides around 60,000 sandwiches to people in need. The platform Munch is also about to launch a service for economically vulnerable groups. It focuses on saving food and provides a platform for restaurants and retailers to offer unsold but high-quality food with a 40-60% discount. Moreover, it has a partnership with the Hungarian Food Bank (MunCharity) to provide food to families in need.

The organization Heroes of Responsible Dining has a much broader scope of action than the abovementioned initiatives. Its main goal is to help catering companies and restaurants work in a more environment-friendly way and provide them with sustainability certifications. The organisation also encourages people to buy organically and sustainably grown products, coming from local producers, while also promoting food education. For instance, they organise courses for teachers to introduce the topic of sustainable eating in schools.

Other types of initiatives focus on food production and urban gardening. For instance, Auróra Klímakert és közösségi komposztáló (Auróra Climate Garden and community composter) is a

community garden which aims at strengthening the fertility of their soils through composting and planting trees to mitigate climate change effects in the urban environment.

Finally, the food strategy in the 19th district of Budapest aims at improving the quality of life of its inhabitants by promoting urban food production involving marginalised and vulnerable groups and enhancing the presence of local food markets to increase the availability of good and sustainably produced food. This food strategy also promotes the diffusion of community gardens and in particular of “district orchards” to strengthen the community and make food available to everyone. Although this strategy has not been translated into practice effectively so far, it provides guidelines that can be implemented in the future.

3.7 LISBON

Table 8: Overview of Lisbon Planning Frameworks, Policies and Initiatives

TYPE	TITLE	MAIN FOCUS	INITIATOR	TIME TIME FRAME	C	L	I	C
National Policy	Innovation Agenda for Agriculture 2030 - Terra Futura	Agricultural market	State	2020-2030				
City-region food-related policy	Strategy 2030 LMA		Municipality	2020-2030				
City-region food policy	Terras Cascais Strategy de	Sustainable food systems from farm to fork; food education: local economy	Municipality	2009-ongoing				

Planning Framework	Cascais Municipal Master Plan	Land use and sustainable development	State	1997-ongoing				
Initiative	Cozinha com Alma	Provide meals to needy families	Association of Solidarity Cooking and Meals with Soul	2011				
Initiative	Fruta Feia	Recover food from discarded fruits and vegetables	Isabel Soares who participated at a social entrepreneurs hip contest “Ideias de Origem Portuguesa”	2013				
Initiative	REFOOD	Food salvage and donation	Hunter Halder, who first started collecting food	2011				
Initiative	Fruit Heroes® – Healthy School Snacks Heróis da Fruta®	Promote healthy food habits	Portuguese Association Against Childhood Obesity	2011				
Initiative	Sintra Grows Healthy (SGH) Sintra Cresce Saudável	Promote healthy lifestyles in primary schools		2017				
Initiative	Agroparque das Terras da Costa e do Mar		Municipality of Almada	From 2022 to 2025				

Food policies and planning framework

Food production and environmental services play a significant role in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. Almost 40% of the area's land is used for agriculture (including pasture) and a total of 12% of all the food produced in Portugal for national consumption comes from the city-region. However, the development of a sustainable and resilient food system is still in its early stages. To uptake such a development a range of food-related policies and a comprehensive Food Transition Strategy have been put in place. These policies and the strategic framework are specifically designed to prioritise health, environmental considerations, and the promotion of food sustainability, the resilience of the regional food system as well as the support of urban and rural agriculture.

The Cascais Municipal Master Plan represents a strategic political tool for comprehensive spatial planning in the Cascais area, part of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. This **planning framework** aims to regulate land use and foster sustainable urban development and management within the municipality. The plan plays a crucial role in shaping Cascais' city-region food systems and community cohesion by providing a framework for urban agriculture and emphasizing self-sufficiency. The Municipal Master Plan generates several *co-benefits*. For instance, it promotes sustainable land use practices, ensuring the conservation of biodiversity and providing green spaces for urban (community) agriculture. Additionally, its primary goal is to create a large green pocket in Vale de Caparide which contributes to environmental sustainability and prevents heat island effects in Cascais. The plan also supports cultural and environmental tourism, such as the renowned Carcavelos Wine. *Linkages* between land use planning and water management are achieved through the revitalisation of the hydrological structures within the municipality. In terms of *inclusion*, it also prioritises social cohesion by providing opportunities for accessing land for urban agriculture to vulnerable communities.

A pivotal **national policy** in the pursuit of food system transformation is the Innovation Agenda for Agriculture 2030 – Terra Futura. By emphasizing innovation and forward-thinking sustainable approaches, Terra Futura aims to drive advancements in agricultural practices, enhance productivity, promote sustainable and resilient food production systems, and generate employment opportunities. Environmentally, this policy supports sustainable agricultural practices including soil conservation, efficient water and energy use, reduction of atmospheric pollutants, and the preservation of biodiversity. On a social level, the policy encourages the adoption of the Mediterranean diet, thereby improving public health outcomes and raising awareness about food quality and regional food products. Additionally, the policy supports family farming and strives for gender equality within the agricultural sector. In terms of *linkages*, the policy aims to establish strong *connections* between city inhabitants, farmers, and the public administration. The policy also emphasises the *inclusion* of young farmers by providing support, resources, and financial opportunities. The *connectivities* to other scales, sectors, and institutions are established through cooperation between various sectoral policies and intergovernmental departments.

Another significant **city-region food policy** that further supports the objectives of Terra Futura is the LMA Strategy 2030. This strategy provides a comprehensive roadmap for sustainable development in the region by outlining key initiatives, targets, and actions that aim to promote sustainable food systems, enhance regional cooperation, and foster *inclusive* and balanced growth. Developed through a public consultation process, the strategy applies specifically to the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. Its overarching objective is to enhance metropolitan food resilience by promoting the establishment of short food supply chains, fostering sustainable consumption patterns through education, modernising markets, and implementing green and sustainable public procurement for school canteens. Furthermore, the strategy places great emphasis on soil preservation by diversifying non-agricultural activities on farms which contributes to its environmental benefits. Approximately 15% of the metropolitan area's food supply is meant to be secured through sustainable production methods, innovative water management solutions, low carbon distribution networks, and proximity food circuits. *Linkages* include the development of the policy-oriented framework for food transition focused on integrating territorial management into agricultural production and land management practices and thus aligning food security with economic and environmental objectives. The policy also seeks to empower marginalised and vulnerable groups (such as economically deprived neighbourhoods) through training activities like skills-building programs. *Connections* to other scales, sectors and institutions are fostered through spatial planning initiatives, local development programs, and partnerships with private and civic organizations.

Finally, the Terras de Cascais Strategy stands as another notable example of a transformative **city-regional food policy**. The strategy centres around the Community Gardens project, which actively involves residents in decision-making processes in the Cascais municipality. Through its implementation, the strategy has achieved remarkable outcomes across various sustainability dimensions. Environmentally, for instance, the strategy promotes regenerative and organic farming practices and provides courses about sustainable production practices. Ensuring access to land has also economically benefited city inhabitants who can produce their own vegetables. Furthermore, it encourages local markets to commercialise locally produced organic food products which supports the local economy and small-scale farmers. In terms of *linkages*, the strategy establishes connections between urban and rural areas by setting spaces for food production within the municipality, promoting short food supply chains and supporting small-scale organic farmers. The Terras de Cascais Strategy also places a strong emphasis on *inclusion* – particularly for vulnerable populations who cannot afford to purchase organic food products – by creating production sites freely accessible to every resident of Cascais and producing organic and fresh food for food-aid institutions. Finally, *connectivity* is fostered through collaborations among various municipal departments and organisations – for instance, through partnerships with the education department to establish school vegetable gardens or with prison establishments to involve inmates in food production.

Initiatives

Almost all the analysed initiatives in Lisbon were started more than 10 years ago by local associations except for Sintra which was initiated in 2017. Lisbon's city-region initiatives are centred around three main goals: reducing food waste, helping food-insecure families, and promoting healthy habits among children.

Reducing food waste is the aim of ReFood which collects food from supermarkets, hotels, and restaurants and redistributes them to food-insecure families. ReFood Centres can be established in a neighbourhood by anyone which encourages grassroots ownership. The initiative also works in close contact with local networks of public and private social service providers, churches and religious groups and private businesses. Another example is Furta Feia which recovers fruits and vegetables directly from farms and orchards that are discarded due to their appearance and resells them at low prices making them accessible for low-income families – although cafes and restaurants can also buy these products at lower prices.

Other initiatives focus on supporting food-insecure families like, for instance, the initiative Cozinha com Alma by supplying nutritious meals at a fair price to families in economic distress. They specifically target those in need who, because of embarrassment over having financial problems, are less inclined to seek assistance through conventional channels. Cozinha not only provides food, but it also runs a programme to support people of working age in job search and another one that supports people over 65 years.

Other initiatives like Heróis da Fruta® (Fruit Heroes) and Sintra Cresce Saudável (Sintra Grows Healthy) aim at raising awareness about healthy food. Both initiatives focus on school children through education programmes and providing healthy meals at schools. Whereas Heróis da Fruta® works with teachers and municipalities' nutritionists to increase the number of portions of fruit and vegetables consumed per day by school children; Sintra Grows Healthy engages the community to promote healthy lifestyles in primary schools through classes on food education, healthy meals in canteens to improve children's nutrition and promotion of physical activity to improve motor skills. In addition, they organise school visits to vegetable gardens and composting labs.

Finally, the Agroparque das Terras da Costa e do Mar is a peri-urban park of 200 hectares created in 2022 that is devoted to sustainable agricultural production. Its aim is to provide fresh products to the Lisbon metropolitan area. Indeed, the construction of "food hubs" is planned to facilitate the commercialisation for local farmers. This initiative will contribute to providing a decent lifestyle to farmers and offer job opportunities to marginalised and vulnerable groups and it will *connect* the park with the tourist sector of Caparica. The peri-urban park will also promote education on food-related topics by organising activities for children.

3.8 PLAIN OF LUCCA

Table 9: Overview of Plain of Lucca Planning Frameworks, Policies and Initiatives

TYPE	TITLE	MAIN FOCUS	INITIATOR	TIME FRAME	C L I C			
					C	L	I	C
City-region food policy	School meals in Capannori and Lucca	Sustainable public food procurement in Capannori and Lucca	Municipalities and schools	Since 2005 Capannori since 2009 Lucca				
City-region food policy	"Centomila orti in Toscana"	Urban gardening in Tuscany	Region	Since 2016				
National food policy	Minimum Environmental Criteria for Public Procurement (CAM-Criteri Minimi Ambientali)	Sustainable public food procurement in Italy	Government-led	Since 2008				
Planning framework	The 'Piana del cibo' planning framework	Food governance	5 municipalities	Since 2019				
Initiative	Calafata	Viticulture, oliviculture, horticulture, orchards cultivation, beekeeping, cultivation of herbs.		2011				

		Access to jobs for vulnerable people. Food provision to solidarity shop						
Initiative	Fattoria degli Albogatti	Peri-urban agriculture, access to gardening for people with difficult socio-economic conditions Educational activities (on nature, food and agriculture) for children and their parents		2009				
Initiative	ConServe	Reduction of food waste Job opportunities for vulnerable workers	La Calafata, l'Unitaria and l'Odissea coops, Caritas	2018				
Initiative	Rete Lucca Biodinamica	Biodynamic agriculture Exchange of equipment and know-how between partners	13 biodynamic wine producers and retailers of Lucca province	2016				
Initiative	Solidarity Purchase Group of Network	Connect producers and consumers to work together in	Network of subjects active in the field of	2009				

	Lucca (Rete GAS Lucchesi)	food production Connection with other solidarity networks	solidarity economy					
Initiative	Farmers' markets	Access to market for small local farmers	Municipalities, farmers associations	2008				

Food policies and planning framework

In the Plain of Lucca, five municipalities (Capannori, Lucca, Altopascio, Porcari and Villa Basilica) are committed to guarantee a local sustainable food production which is safe, reduces environmental damage and waste, increases the resilience of the local food system, and contributes to the economic development of the region. The municipalities aim also to improve distribution, encouraging the direct relationship between consumer and producer, and guarantee a right to food for all people living in the territory.

To do so the cities agreed to follow a set of principles, goals and actions, outlined in a common food strategy, namely a coordinated and participatory food policy management initiative called “Piana del Cibo” (Plain of Food). This cross-cutting strategic **planning framework** aims to increase the well-being of people living in the area and to promote sustainable development. Food is considered as a leverage for broader transformative change in the city-region, with special attention to urban gardens through which abandoned areas can be reconverted, access to food can be improved and social *inclusion* encouraged. The planning framework aims to establish new *linkages* by incentivizing local food production and through the recovery of abandoned land. In doing so, it aims to contribute to the local economic development and promote the cultural identity and historical heritage connected to the landscape. This planning framework is jointly managed by the five municipalities and entails a participatory governance, composed of the “Agorà” – i.e. an open entity, designed to encourage participation by civil society and other food system stakeholders. An additional entity, currently being reorganised, is the Food Policy Office which is a day-to-day coordination and support organism.

When considering urban gardens in particular, another relevant **city-regional policy**, issued by the Tuscany region, is the “Centomila orti in Toscana” (hundred thousand vegetable gardens in Tuscany) which aims to implement a virtuous model of urban community gardening involving local associations and young people. Lucca, Capannori and Altopascio took part in the project in 2016,

and Lucca, for instance, created four urban gardens on Municipality-owned land and fourteen school gardens. As part of this policy, urban gardens are considered as a space for strengthening community relationships as well as a regenerative means to give new life to abandoned spaces; hence, promoting a sustainable approach to land use and food cultivation. In this regard, people involved in food growing activities must follow the guidelines stated by the Region in “A guide to practical horticulture”. For instance, the management of the garden by an NGO or working group is mandatory, while the cultivation of local varieties, the application of organic farming principles, and the organization of educational activities are voluntary. The selection process to access the urban gardens contains award criteria for low-income and/or unemployed applicants, and for families with two or more children. In Capannori, special attention is dedicated to the *inclusion* of people with disabilities. The Piana del Cibo also dedicates specific attention to public food procurement opportunities.

When considering this area of intervention, in Italy, Environmental Minimum Criteria (Criteri minimi ambientali- CAMs) represent a **national policy**, a guideline for public administration to write and execute tenders. Specifically, CAMs consist of a set of technical specifications, award criteria and contract clauses aimed at enhancing the environmental and social dimensions of sustainability in public tenders. Although the CAMs started as voluntary criteria, they became compulsory in 2016 and were reformed in 2020 to introduce a more careful consideration of the different types of canteen services and food supply, identifying different criteria according to the contexts (e.g., kindergartens, schools, universities, hospitals, prisons). CAMs also address social issues like labour conditions in agriculture. Furthermore, menus are designed considering the national public health guidelines and the sustainability impact of the meals – e.g., by preventing food waste or providing plant-based proteins. According to the last report by the independent observatory FoodInsider (2022), the CAMs have improved the overall sustainability of public food procurement and effectively increased the quality of the Italian school meals, in terms of nutritional quality of the food.

Moreover, the Plain of Lucca has implemented a **city-regional policy**, which sets very ambitious sustainability criteria for public procurement for school canteen services (e.g., seasonality, education, waste reduction) through new arrangements, with a strong focus on short food supply chains. Over the last decades, Lucca and Capannori worked on several projects that steadily steered the attention towards the quality and sustainability of the food provided by the collective catering. Capannori, for instance, has progressively strengthened the role of the local School Canteens Committees, the educational role of school canteen service and increased the quality of the school meals in terms of nutrition and environmental sustainability. This process started in 2005 with a project called “Quality canteens” to make school meals healthier and more nutritious, followed by many other food education projects, like “I love colazione” (I love breakfast), “Mangia giusto, muovi con gusto!” (eat well and move with taste) and “Dire, Fare, Partecipare” (Say, Do, Participate). In 2014, the Municipality of Capannori and Cirfood (the enterprise winner of the tender for school canteens in Capannori) started a new process to improve the quality of the service.

Also due to a committee of parents not fully satisfied with the service, in 2016 the municipality adopted the **city-regional policy**, called “Patto per il cibo” (Food Pact), which highlighted the importance of school canteens for food education and healthy and sustainable food provision, while intervening to increase the quality of the service itself. Capannori increased the provision of local food thanks to an agreement signed in 2017 between the Municipality, the collective catering Cir Food and the local agricultural cooperative L'Unitaria. In the same year the Municipality of Capannori also developed a convention with Giubilesi monitoring society (renewed in 2022) to keep improving the quality of school canteen services. Likewise, in Lucca, between 2009 and 2015, two projects promoted the consumption of local, healthy, and sustainable food among school children and their families.

Initiatives

In the Plain of Lucca there are both older initiatives, founded in 2008/2009, and younger ones from 2016 and 2018. They were started thanks to local municipalities, mainly Lucca and Capannori, as well as by grassroots associations. Most of the initiatives focus on supporting local agriculture, encouraging agroecological production practices and *linking* urban and rural areas.

Initiatives like Rete Lucca Biodinamica (Biodynamic Network Lucca) and Calafata Cooperative promote agroecological farming practices in the area. Rete Lucca Biodinamica was created by 13 biodynamic wine producers of the Lucca province who aim to promote the uptake of biodynamic agricultural practices, while providing support to their members through the exchange of equipment and know-how and helping them to promote their products. Calafata is an agricultural social cooperative. The cooperative uses formerly abandoned lands and, at the same time, offers job opportunities to vulnerable workers, such as migrants and former inmates, and provides fresh products to solidarity shops. To do so, it collaborates with many local projects, both in the social and in the food spheres. Conserve is another initiative Calafata works with. Conserve aims at transforming fruits and vegetables which can't be sold as fresh products due to aesthetic defects. In addition, they organise educational activities for children, they foster access to work for people with mental health issues and beneficiaries of social measures.

Another initiative that focuses on production is the association Albogatti Farm which was developed on public land and comprises individual allotments and collective gardening. Participants are expected to adopt sustainable cultivation techniques and contribute to the realisation of educational activities to create awareness around environmental protection, biodiversity, food and nutrition among urban dwellers.

Caritas Lucca is central to several food aid interventions in the area such as canteens for vulnerable groups and food aid packages distribution. The latter is progressively being replaced with a model called Empori Solidali (or solidarity food shops) which function similarly to food banks. In these

shops, vulnerable groups can find products for free (the amount allocated varies based on various criteria) and Caritas is working to make available more items which can be locally procured.

Finally, concerning local food access and distribution there are various farmers markets in the region of Lucca and a Solidarity Purchase Group Network of Lucca (Rete GAS Lucchesi). The latter comprises three distribution points in different neighbourhoods in Lucca in which fresh food products are brought by farmers. This network aims at creating a network of farmers and consumers, discussing food-related issues and supporting local and sustainable food production together. Moreover, they are *connected* to other solidarity-based purchase groups and solidarity networks to provide food to vulnerable people such as undocumented immigrants. Small-scale farmers may also sell their products at the local farmers' markets such as Foro Boario market, Mercato della Terra or Coldiretti Market "Campagna amica" in Lucca.

4. KEY INSIGHTS FROM THE LIVING LABS: LESSONS LEARNED FOR RESILIENT AND SUSTAINABLE CITY-REGION FOOD SYSTEMS

Urban and rural areas across Europe face challenges in ensuring equitable access to healthy, safe, and sustainable food. A city-region food system is an inclusive and integrated approach that links rural and urban communities within a region, promoting sustainable practices in food production and consumption, and nurturing local food cultures and traditions. To foster a resilient and sustainable city-region food system, it is crucial to guide the implementation of emerging food policies, planning frameworks, and initiatives at the local, regional, and national levels with an integrated food policy landscape. This approach must transcend the limitations of incremental interventions commonly observed in policy-making and siloed policies and instead prioritize the eradication of key systemic barriers entrenched within the food system that have a direct impact on vulnerable communities.

In light of the extensive work conducted by the FoodCLIC Living Labs during the gap analysis phase, a set of lessons learned has been derived. These lessons are drawn from the Living Labs' analysis of planning frameworks, food policies and initiatives, which has revealed key barriers, identified learning needs, and existing expertise within Living Labs, within the framework of the CLIC Framework.

A critical insight presented from the Matrix of Barriers, Learning Needs and Expertise (please see Annex 1) is the significant barrier identified by Living Labs concerning co-benefits. This barrier manifests as a lack of integration between policies and initiatives related to diverse policy domains such as urban development and planning, economy, health, and food and justice. To address this challenge, there is a pressing need to prioritize the shared understanding of sustainable food practices. Additionally, there is a need to increase competencies that enable a global perspective on sustainability and to enhance skills related to food system impact evaluation, including justice dimensions. In terms of linkages, it becomes evident that a notable issue is the inadequate representation of various actors and resources within the food system. To overcome this barrier, there emerges a need to gather comprehensive data and expertise from a wide array of stakeholders within the food system, particularly to the domain of short food supply chains. Some Living Labs, such as Berlin, have displayed promise in strengthening rural-urban linkages through initiatives like

community-supported agriculture and local organic farming. In the context of inclusion, the central barrier is engaging marginalized and vulnerable communities. According to the Living Labs, stakeholders in food systems frequently lack common goals, trust, and effective communication required for achieving inclusive food governance. Consequently, to foster inclusion a need to identify and involve a broader spectrum of stakeholders in the process of policy development has been identified. This entails fostering participatory methods and collecting information pertinent to vulnerable groups as also discussed in the lessons learnt presented in this chapter. Finally, the issue of connectivities remains a prominent challenge. A considerable number of food-related initiatives in the eight city-regions encounter barriers due to a siloed approach to policymaking, often exacerbated by a deficiency of competencies within local governments. A shortage of physical spaces and participatory opportunities for stakeholders to convene and collaborate has been also highlighted. In tackling these issues, Living Labs agree on the necessity to facilitate networking, enhance communication, and promote information exchange among all stakeholders engaged in the food system. Building trust, investing in leadership, and instituting multi-level governance structures emerge as essential steps.

With these key insights from the Living Labs Matrix of Barriers, Learning Needs and Expertise, we present actionable pathways for addressing the needs and gaps identified in the eight city-regions towards resilient and sustainable city-region food systems. These lessons learned are aligned with the broader mission of the EU's sustainable food systems policy frameworks, such as the European Green Deal, the Farm to Fork Strategy, Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and the Circular Economy Action Plan. Through the application of these lessons, policymakers have the potential to facilitate the advancement of sustainable and resilient city-region food systems, impacting not only FoodCLIC city-regions but also resonating far beyond its boundaries.

#1: Ensure Integrated and Inclusive Governance with Multi-Stakeholder Engagement and Cross-Sector Collaboration

The complexity of food-related issues necessitates integrated, inclusive and systemic approaches that embrace the interconnections between different dimensions of sustainability, as well as sectors and scales and people. This entails considering the broader system encompassing the entire lifecycle of food products and services, spanning processing, transportation, distribution, consumption, and disposal and how it interacts with other systems including healthcare for example. To achieve this, food-related policies and planning frameworks should adopt a multi-stakeholder approach, ensuring that diverse perspectives and communities (business, research, community) are included in policy development and implementation on different scales from local, to regional and national legislations.

In this project, we found that cross-sectoral collaboration across different policy areas and sectors including agriculture, procurement, health, environment, urban planning, and welfare is crucial to recognise sustainability trade-offs and their unintended consequences (such as social equity or economic growth). Examples illustrating this approach can be found in the report, including Amsterdam's 'City Deal Policy,' Aarhus' 'Government's Strategy for Food, Meals, and Health,' Barcelona's 'Special Plan for the Protection and Improvement of the Baix Llobregat Agricultural Park,' and Lisbon's 'Cascais Municipal Master Plan'.

Furthermore, creating inclusive food systems and fostering participatory food governance is essential for addressing the diverse needs of communities. Policymakers should prioritize integrating vulnerable communities, including rural communities and small-scale farmers, as well as those with varying nutritional needs. To achieve this, a multifaceted approach is needed. For example, actions can be considered to help ensure access to healthy and sustainable food and could begin with the formulation and revision of national dietary guidelines. These guidelines, as seen in the example of the Danish Official Dietary Guidelines, might take into account cost-prohibitive factors that can sometimes hinder low-income consumers from accessing healthy food. Furthermore, policies should be carefully designed to confront food insecurity and poverty while accommodating the unique nutritional needs of different population segments, including children, the elderly, and those with specific cultural food preferences. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Brasov's 'Education for healthy life for Romanian children' and Amsterdam's 'Memorandum on Health policy'. Implementing healthy, free food provisions in public institutions such as schools, care homes, detention centres, and health facilities is crucial, as is reducing the stigma around food assistance, particularly for lower-income communities. This is demonstrated in the example of several food initiatives presented in this report including Berlin's 'Netzwerk der LebensMittelPunkteand', the online platform for food redistribution 'Foodsharing.de', and 'Cozinha con Alma' in Cascais.

#2: Enhance Sustainability Co-Benefits through Evidence and Fair Resource Allocation

Presenting concrete evidence regarding the economic returns from sustainable food practices is a vital step to enhance sustainability co-benefits. Sustainable initiatives and policies often struggle to provide clear evidence of their return on investment. Demonstrating the economic advantages and showcasing the social and environmental impacts justifies public expenditures in this regard. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Aarhus' 'Climate-friendly Dietary Guidelines'; Amsterdam's 'City Deal Policy Plan' and Lisbon's 'Innovation Agenda for Agriculture 2030 - Terra Futura'. Achieving this might involve adopting an inclusive approach for measuring sustainability impact in the definitions, methodologies, and indicators developed for monitoring and assessing the

effectiveness of food policies and planning frameworks. Consequently, integrating indicators that focus on food justice and community resilience in the policy monitoring and accountability mechanism becomes essential. This approach ensures that the public sector not only monitors but also actively addresses sustainability co-benefits, preventing the simple outsourcing of essential services such as food aid and poverty alleviation to third-sector organizations.

Moreover, addressing the concentration of power within large food retail value chains is pivotal to shift toward more inclusive food policies. Thus, addressing power dynamics within policy formulation necessitates recognizing the influential role of the food industry and vested economic interests. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Brasov's 'Public Markets Administration Service Braşov - Decision of Local Council no. 428/ 09.07.2022' and 'Flywheel markets'. To foster a fair and transformative food system, it is also imperative for local and regional governments to guarantee funding to encourage social innovation and experimentation at the local level. This should have a specific focus on recognizing and addressing the systemic challenges faced by vulnerable groups. For example, Aarhus Municipality is supporting 'Skraldecafeen', a community-run socio-economic kitchen that recovers food waste from local supermarkets; Barcelona City Council has founded 'Espai participatiu Agròpolis' to raise awareness on the benefits of short circuits and to foster the development of autonomous agri-food systems and in Berlin, the Ministry of Health and the District of Reinickendorf are among the founders of 'Hilfelotse Berlin', a web platform that provides information on food banks. Finally, the allocation of resources – be it financial support, or access to resources such as land – significantly contributes to the realization of sustainability co-benefits. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Barcelona's 'PEAC - Strategic Food Plan of Catalonia 2021-2026' and Lisbon's 'Cascais Municipal Master Plan' and 'Innovation Agenda for Agriculture 2030 - Terra Futura'.

#3: Take Measures to Guarantee Regulations for Healthy Food Environments

Robust regulatory frameworks are essential for creating healthy and sustainable food environments. In public canteens, public food procurement should include minimum mandatory sustainability standards, like quotas for organic and regional food products, while incorporating food education, including cooking classes, in public tenders for children and students cultivating healthy eating habits from an early age. Example illustrating this approach can be found in Berlin's Food Strategy, Budapest's 'Government Decree 676/2020 (XII. 28.) on special rules for public procurement procedures for public catering', and Italian's Criteri Minimi Ambientali.

It is equally essential to prioritize measures that prevent the concentration of catering services in the hands of a few private businesses (for example, the initiatives 'Xamec and Xarxa agroecològica

de Menjadors Escolars de Catalunya' provide healthy, seasonal and organic food to school canteens in Catalonia). Furthermore, strengthening the regulatory framework that mandates retailers and catering companies to maintain a minimum threshold of local production, along with the development of processing infrastructure like local abattoirs and dairy facilities, strengthens the resilience of local food networks and economies. This, in turn, fosters stronger urban-rural food connections, ultimately contributing to more sustainable and economically resilient communities. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Berlin Food Strategy, Budapest's Government Decree 676/2020 (XII. 28.) on special rules for public procurement procedures for public catering and Plain of Lucca's 'Piana del cibo' planning framework.

Similarly, it is important to encourage sustainable and healthy food consumption through taxation, levies, and incentives to make healthy food environments stronger. For example, providing financial incentives to workplaces and businesses that offer healthy meal options in their cafeterias, such as subsidized fresh fruits and vegetables, can encourage employees to make healthier food choices (examples illustrating this approach can be found in Budapest's 'Government Decree 676/2020 (XII. 28.) on special rules for public procurement procedures for public catering' and Budapest's 'Freely accessible web-based registry of small-scale farmers and food produced by small-scale farmers'. Another example can be found in Portugal, where the Directorate-General of Health supports the project 'Fruit Heroes® – Healthy School Snacks | Heróis da Fruta®' whose aim is to increase the number of portions of fruit and vegetables consumed by school children aged between 3 to 11 years. Similarly, the Municipality of Sintra set up the initiative 'Sintra Grows Healthy (SGH) | Sintra Cresce Saudável' to promote food education and physical activities in schools).

Rethinking urban planning frameworks to accommodate the emergence and establishment of local food system logistics and networks can also significantly optimize the layout of farmers' street markets, Community Supported Agriculture pick-up points, urban farming gardens and school canteens. For example, the development of transportation networks and efficient food storage facilities in rural areas is essential, as is providing support for local producers through financial aid and public recognition. This combined approach could streamline efforts to diversify food production and distribution, making local food also more accessible to vulnerable populations and strengthening linkages between urban and rural regions. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Brasov's 'Flywheel markets', Budapest's 'Call for tenders for agricultural leasehold properties' and Barcelona's 'Special plan for the protection and improvement of the Baix Llobregat Agricultural Park (2003) Review of the Special Plan (2015).

Finally, regulations can also be leveraged to develop minimum standards for community-led food infrastructures such as community gardens, food-sharing initiatives and neighbourhood kitchens.

These regulations could encompass various aspects, including the allocation of dedicated land within urban areas for community use, the designation of zones for communal activities like gardening and cooking, and guidelines allowing local community groups to redistribute surplus food safely and without facing penalties. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Budapest's '2030 Long-term Urban Development Concept' and Plain of Lucca's 'Centomila Orti in Toscana' and 'Piana del Cibo'. In Amsterdam, the initiative 'More than Milk Amsterdam' is among the funders of the soil alliance, which allows citizens to take a share in the countryside surrounding Amsterdam.

#4: Strengthen City-Region Food Systems through urban rural connections

In the context of urban-rural dynamics, several critical considerations emerged as a result of the analysis. The ageing farming population juxtaposed with the desire of young people to engage in agriculture highlights a need to address challenges related to access to land and finances. Often, current policies focus on reinforcing existing community relationships, missing opportunities to foster new connections spanning urban, rural, and various sectors such as environment, finance, transport, and economy. To rectify this, policies should be designed to facilitate cross-sectoral connections, unlocking synergies and shared objectives to make farming a profitable and desirable profession. For instance, strategic partnerships with the financial sector in rural development initiatives can stimulate interest and investment in farms located in rural areas. Encouraging young people to pursue careers in rural farming to revitalize rural traditions, drive innovation, and preserve biodiversity through practices should be a focal point of agricultural-related policies. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Barcelona's 'Baix Llobregat Agricultural Park', Budapest, Brasov's 'Education for Healthy Life for Romanian Children program' and Plain of Lucca's 'Piana del Cibo'. In Aarhus, they aim to attract young people in the agricultural sector by showing the everyday life of young farmers through the Instagram channel '@derforlandmand'. In Barcelona 'Banc de Terres' helps the transfer of abandoned land to whoever is interested in buying it, prioritising young farmers.

Furthermore, promoting regional produce, food origin transparency, and short food supply chains stand as cornerstones of city-region food systems. To achieve these objectives, it is necessary to include quantifiable benchmarks for regional products in public food tenders, incentivize agricultural cooperatives, local consumption through farmers' markets and CSA, and protect local economies through certification schemes (e.g., certified local) and online platforms that connect local producers with consumers. Amplifying the importance of local sourcing and transparency empowers consumers to make environmentally and socially conscious choices. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Brasov's 'Flywheel Markets' and Budapest's Freely accessible web-based registry of small-scale farmers and food produced by small-scale farmers. In

Berlin, the platform 'Foodsharing.de' allows users to find nearby free food, also in the form of peer-to-peer food sharing. In Budapest, the organization 'Heroes of Responsible Dining' fosters caterings and restaurants to buy organically and sustainably grown products, coming from local producers. In the Plain of Lucca many initiatives are focused on promoting local products, such as 'Calfata', 'Fattoria degli Albogatti', 'Rete Lucca Biodinamica', 'Rete GAS Lucchesi' and especially the 'Farmer Markets' that have been established in different parts of the Plain of Lucca.

Strategic awareness campaigns, staged in food retailers, can nudge consumers to buy local products, support farmers and inspire an interest in agriculture, especially among younger generations. For example, 'Mellemfolk Cafe' sets up events and seminars to raise awareness on local cooperatives and the agricultural landscape of Denmark while also organizing a distribution point for farmers to sell their products. Also 'Cuchara', Barcelona, fosters food education to help people make informed food choices. Finally, to ensure access to short food supply chains for the most vulnerable, targeted food vouchers and prescriptions can be provided to communities experiencing restricted access to fresh regional products. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Brasov's Public Markets Administration Service Braşov - Decision of Local Council no. 428/09.07.2022 as well as initiatives such as 'Calafata' in Plain of Lucca. The community garden 'Voedseltuin IJplein', Amsterdam, is located in a low-income neighbourhood and allows its inhabitants to grow fresh and organic products. Similarly, the organization 'Farmers for Neighbours' and 'More Than Milk Amsterdam' aim at providing fresh and healthy food to vulnerable communities. Other examples are: 'La Botiga del Prat' and 'Fundacio Espigoladors' in Barcelona, 'Arena Chefs, Out of Passion for PEOPLE' in Brasov, 'Auróra Klímakert és közösségi komposztáló', 'Te meg Én' tanoda and 'Heti betevő' in Budapest.

#5 Prioritise place-based solutions

Recognizing and harnessing the expertise of people in shaping policies that encompass the diverse needs and aspirations of communities is of utmost importance. This goal can be achieved through the allocation of core funding to create and support Local Food Policy Councils, Food Hubs, and Community-based Initiatives that actively involve all relevant actors in the city-region food system. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Amsterdam's 'Food Connects', 'Berlin Food Policy Council' and 'Food Council of the Plain of Lucca' as well as in some initiatives including 'Voedseltuin IJplein' and 'Bloei & Groei' in Amsterdam, 'Netzwerk der LebensmittelPun' and 'Über den Tellerrand' in Berlin, 'Agroparque das Terras da Costa e do Mar', Lisbon, 'Solidarity Purchase Group Network of Lucca (Rete GAS Lucchesi)', Plain of Lucca.

These organizations, many of which operate as informal self-organized networks, provide essential spaces for diverse stakeholders to collaborate and drive transformative changes within the food system. This entails local, regional, and national governments providing funding to sustain these initiatives, which frequently rely on volunteers and donations. By involving these organizations, policies can be rooted in the actual needs and realities of individuals and communities. Through cross-sectoral cooperation, these initiatives can serve as bridges between people and governments, providing strategic advice to policymakers and implementing policies on the ground with greater acceptance and effectiveness. For example, many local governments in the Barcelona city-region support the initiative 'Terra Pagesa', with the goal of facilitating the connection between conventional and organic local producers and food shops.

Understanding that communities have the best insight into their unique challenges, support for local self-organization is also necessary. Providing tools, resources, finances, and information would enable neighbourhoods and communities to tackle challenges on the ground. This decentralized approach would not only boost community-led experimentation and innovation but also guarantee that policies remain place-based, relevant, and useful. To enhance these efforts, the creation and maintenance of databases encompassing food policies, networks, initiatives, and urban planning maps would greatly assist these organizations in collaboration and coordinated activities at different levels of food governance.

It is also crucial to integrate regular consultations, public hearings, feedback mechanisms, and opportunities for direct engagement of people as integral components of the policy-making process. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Aarhus's 'Municipality Plan', Berlin's 'Neighbourhood Management Program', Barcelona's governing body of the 'Baix Llobregat Agricultural Park' and participatory food governance model composed of the 'Agorà' in Plain of Lucca. In the case of initiatives, in Barcelona, the 'Espai participatiu Agropolis' has the explicit goal of influencing public policies to promote short and sustainable food value chains. Another example is the initiative 'Banc de Terres' which helps the connection and information exchange between the Municipalities in the Barcelona area and old and new owners of the land.

Continuity of food-related policies must also be secured beyond specific political mandates by developing dedicated offices and building the capacity of the administrative staff at all governance levels as demonstrated in the example of Plain of Lucca's food governance planning framework the 'Piana del cibo'.

Finally, to ensure inclusive policy-making, it is vital to centralize the voices of socially and culturally diverse communities. This can be achieved through various means, including policies, planning

frameworks and projects designed to have an immediate impact on their access to food and services. Fostering dialogue through shared surveys that capture lived experiences related to food insecurity and conducting community workshops are some of the effective approaches. Furthermore, appointing food and nutrition ambassadors, including undocumented immigrants and refugees, would significantly contribute to the visibility and representation of vulnerable communities. Examples illustrating this approach can be found in Berlin's 'Neighbourhood management program' (Quartiersmanagement Berlin) and Lisbon's 'LMA Strategy 2030'. In addition, an initiative that facilitates this approach is 'Farmers for Neighbours (Amsterdam)', where the volunteers coming from the community have the possibility of becoming coordinators, which reinforces local leadership and management. In Berlin, for example, the civil society association 'Ernährungsrat Berlin e.V.' represent the local community, including migrants and marginalized people, in the public spaces advocating for better food policies. Similarly, facilitating connections between migrant communities and regional farms can be pivotal for economic integration. For example, establishing an administrative fast track for small food businesses, particularly those led by women, migrants, refugees, and artisans, would serve as a crucial avenue for creating inclusive, equitable, and place-based food systems. In Amsterdam, for instance, the initiative 'Bloei & Groei' involves primarily women of colour, and people with mental health issues, in the setting of green spaces for sustainable agriculture. In Berlin, the community kitchen 'Über den Tellerrand' employs migrants in community-building cooking activities. This approach empowers diverse food entrepreneurs, promotes employment opportunities, and facilitates valuable skill exchange.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This report, a collaborative effort within the FoodCLIC project (co-authored by ICLEI ES, Surrey University and FoodCLIC Living Labs), has the goal of providing a comprehensive overview into current and forthcoming urban food-related policies, planning frameworks, and recent initiatives of the eight FoodCLIC city-regions: Aarhus (Denmark), Budapest (Hungary), Brasov (Romania), Berlin (Germany), Plain of Lucca (Italy), Barcelona (Spain), Amsterdam (Netherlands), and Lisbon (Portugal).

Adopting the CLIC framework to analyze the policies, planning frameworks, and initiatives through the lenses of co-benefits, linkages, inclusion, and connectivities, the report emphasises specific policies and planning frameworks in the eight city-regions that have the potential for food system transformation. Indeed, it underscores policies that prioritize sustainability across various facets of the food system, encompassing production, consumption, distribution, and waste management while addressing cross-cutting concerns such as health, nutrition, short food supply chains, climate change, resilience, and social justice.

Furthermore, the report extracts key insights from the gap analysis of food-related policies, planning frameworks, and initiatives, into lessons learned for resilient and sustainable city-region food systems. Key findings discussed in the report highlight the urgent need to address systemic barriers, enhance regulatory frameworks, and promote a balanced integration of sustainability dimensions within city-region food systems. Moreover, fostering diverse and democratic participation in food governance and empowering communities with resources and information is necessary for achieving truly sustainable and equitable urban food environments. The report also sheds light on the intricate web of relationships embedded within food systems, from diverse actors and networks to infrastructures and processes that constitute city-region food systems. Finally, the report also includes a practical insight from the Living Labs about the barriers that Food Policy Networks (FPNs) aim to overcome, and the learning needs they require to achieve transformative food systems within their city-regions.

It is important also to highlight that the mapping and gapping results presented in this report extend beyond city-region boundaries to also encompass national policies that exert an influence on urban food systems transformation. Furthermore, special attention has been given to policies within the domain of urban planning, with a particular focus on urban development, regeneration, and environment – a key thematic thread interwoven throughout the FoodCLIC project that enhances our comprehension of the food policy landscape by integrating the spatial dimension of food and governance.

6. ANNEX 1: MATRIX OF LEARNING NEEDS AND EXPERTISE AMONGST LIVING LABS AND FOOD POLICY NETWORKS

Table 10: Matrix of learning needs and expertise amongst living labs and food policy networks

	BARRIERS	NEEDS	EXISTING EXPERTISE
 C O - B E N E F I T S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Lack of integration between policies and initiatives on urban development, economy, health, and food. •No thorough understanding of how the food system impacts the environment, health, economy, and social justice dimensions. •Not enough integration and coordination among the various stakeholders (research, administration, private sector, and civil society) to preserve the environment and enhance resilience. •Narrow focus on sustainability goals, either people-planet, people-profit, or planet-profit. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To prioritize common well-being and shared understanding and support for sustainable practices. •To cultivate competencies to gain a global perspective on the effects of each activity on the food system sustainability. •To enhance skills in impact evaluation to ensure clearer and more objective assessments of the food policies and interventions. •To build alliances between siloed and disconnected fields. For instance, establishing collaboration with nutrition and health educational programs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Existing FPNs in the city-regions can count on a relevant number of actors who have different expertise and skills such as agriculture, social agriculture, local gastronomy and food traditions, sustainable and healthy Public Food Procurement, food education, urban gardening and social innovation. LLs: Plain of Lucca, Lisbon, Amsterdam

	BARRIERS	NEEDS	EXISTING EXPERTISE
 L I N K A G E S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Lack of proper representation of diverse actors from the food system as well as institutions. •Limited knowledge about key actors, resources, and problems within the food system among existing organizations representing food actors and city inhabitants. • Food policies tend to focus on rural-related challenges, without reference to urban food environments and vice versa. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To create and share more in-depth knowledge about short food supply chains and systems. •To gather comprehensive data and expertise from diverse stakeholders in the food system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •CSA and the local organic farming sector along with urban food hubs contribute to strengthening rural-urban Linkages. LLs: Berlin
	BARRIERS	NEEDS	EXISTING EXPERTISE
 I N C L U	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Stakeholders lacking common goals and expectations, trust among each other and good communication. • Market-based approaches fail to provide food as a social service to marginalized communities. •Lack of participatory and Inclusive approaches in food governance that 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To identify small and large actors in the city-region food systems and attract relevant participants in FPNs. •To involve a broader and more diverse group of stakeholders in the design phase of policies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Poverty networks and food banks can contribute to improving Inclusion and avoiding stigmatization around poverty while local neighbourhood stakeholders work on intercultural and social Inclusion. LLs: Berlin •Engaging with findings from revisions and inputs during the public hearing

<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">S I O N</p>	<p>actively engage deprived and vulnerable groups.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Exacerbated food injustice through the decrease in purchase power. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To foster participatory methods, finding arenas for knowledge co-creation and sharing. •To develop collaborative, transparent and Inclusive approaches to manage food-related knowledge and information. •To gather information and identify needs of vulnerable groups (e.g., establishing food-related indicators such as food insecurity tracking systems). •To give more space to all types of knowledge in addition to the knowledge of policymakers (e.g., in FPNs). 	<p>phase can help with including overlooked dimensions of food governance e.g., Inclusion of vulnerable groups. LLs: Aarhus</p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">BARRIERS</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">NEEDS</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">EXISTING EXPERTISE</p>
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">C O N N E</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Lack of opportunities to meet and talk about initiatives and people’s activities. •Lack of collaboration between actors and Connectivity at different scales hinders FPN establishment. •Lack the competencies within local governments to address transformative policies on food •Siloed way of working in policymaking. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To facilitate networking for actors to collaborate and share information about their activities/capacities/responsibilities, involving professionals from different sectors (e.g., health and nutrition). •To facilitate communication and information exchange between FPN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Knowledge exchange between academia and public administration can help better understand, analyse, monitor and address challenges in the food system. LLs: Barcelona, Berlin, Amsterdam •Exchanges among various governmental departments such as Agriculture and Food Industry, Veterinary and Food Safety,

<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">C T I V I T I E S</p>		<p>actors and other government institutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To organise annual events for stakeholders exchange. •To design tools to improve coordination and collaboration capacities for the public administration, in particular to draw from people suggestions. •To invest in strong leadership and entrepreneurship with support from various sectors (research, administration, private sector, and civil society). •To create multi-level governance (incl. EU, national, regional, city and neighbourhood). • To build on city-region and systemic approaches to food systems in FPNs •To implement trust-building processes and long-term relations. 	<p>Public Health can foster cross-sectoral food policies. LLS: Brasov</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Collaborative spaces within the FPN can facilitate integration and coordination among civil society organizations and local businesses and strengthen their expertise. LLS: Barcelona •The interaction with other FPNs and initiatives can foster exchange of lessons learned, knowledge and expertise and improve their performance. LLS: Amsterdam , Berlin
	<p>BARRIERS</p>	<p>NEEDS</p>	<p>EXISTING EXPERTISE</p>
<p>C R O</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Lack of commitment and resources which reduce engagement and motivation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To strengthen the mediation and negotiation capacity of stakeholders and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Building trust between actors is a key first step to build a FPN. LLS: Amsterdam

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- Overburden on civil society organisations and initiatives which are dependent on short-term project funding.
- Limited resource allocation and intervention capacity of food policies to regulate the unequal impacts of the globalized and market-oriented food industry.
- Limited success of food policies and planning frameworks due to multiple crises, funding competitiveness and diverse political agendas and priorities.

Lack of strategies to help navigate fragmented or polarized political landscapes and risks from electoral and political change.

government departments to ensure capacity-building.

- To improve data availability and sharing to facilitate a common understanding of the food system challenges to wider stakeholders and at diverse levels.
- To foster coherent policy development.
- To carry out internal discussions on how institutionalized the FPNs should be in the city-regions.

- Understanding and using planning frameworks as overarching structures can create effective networks of initiatives. LLs: Aarhus

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Community Supported Agriculture (CSA): means a direct partnership between one or more farmers and the consumers. The latter help to guarantee all or part of the agricultural activity budget, through a pre-financing, they pay in advance their share of the harvest that will take place in the following year, sharing risks and benefits.

City-region food system: It comprises a complex network of actors, processes and relationships to do with food activities that exist in a particular geographical region. This approach includes the explicit perspectives of rural and urban dynamics and needs.

Food-related policies: Policies that engage with food (i.e., policies that mention food) but not as the main focus. Instead, their main focus might be climate, health, etc.

Food policy: is a strategic tool that explicitly covers the topic of food. In an ideal case, it includes a problem statement, a set of objectives and a concrete course of action (implementation action plan), using policy instruments (e.g., laws and (tax) regulations, (urban) land-use planning, investments and subsidy schemes, communication strategies, covenants, etc.) over time with a specified resource allocation. Policies can pertain to bodies of government (such as municipalities), but also to other food system stakeholders. For example, companies can also have food policies for their canteens or the foods they buy, process or sell as part of their business.

Integrated food policies: those that work along all four pillars of the project's CLIC framework, towards an ideal situation in which the policy: (i) realizes sustainability Co-benefits; (ii) establishes Linkages between urban and rural areas; (iii) Includes all relevant food system stakeholders; and (iv) builds Connections between food and other policy domains.

Food Policy Networks (FPNs): network that represent multiple stakeholders and that are either sanctioned by a government body or exist independently of government, and address food-related issues and needs within a city, county, state, tribal, multi-county or other designated region.

Vulnerable and deprived groups: Inclusion of all food system actors and people, while also ensuring a fairer distribution of its outcomes.

Food-sensitive planning framework: includes food priorities in its framework/strategic/vision plan, and its planning process also stipulates processes and mechanisms to engage with questions around food in planning. Given that most cities have one planning framework that addresses all domains/sectors in relation to spatial planning, we are not looking for a planning framework specifically focused on food, but on a planning framework that includes food concerns, i.e. which is food-sensitive.

Initiatives to change urban food systems: are initiatives that produce changes to food environments in the cities and towns involved in the city-region, while also resulting in changes throughout the food system (e.g., the distribution channels, sites of production, etc.). They are similar to “real-life interventions”, which are initiatives to change urban food systems undertaken as part of the FoodCLIC project (see below). They may be distinguished from a food policy if they are more trade-oriented instead of a clear integrated strategic perspective.

REFERENCES

Arcuri S, Belletti G, Bottiglioni S, et al. (2020) Innovazioni istituzionali e approcci multi-attore nelle politiche alimentari Locali: il piano intercomunale per il cibo della Piana di Lucca. In: *Lo Spazio Delle Politiche Locali Del Cibo: Temi, Esperienze e Prospettive*.

Arcuri S, Minotti B and Galli F (2022) Food policy integration in small cities: The case of intermunicipal governance in Lucca, Italy. *Journal of Rural Studies* 89: 287–297. DOI: 10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.12.005.

Arcuri S, Rolandi S, Poiatti M, et al. (Forthcoming) Agri-food sustainable transformative pathways: diving through the evolving territory of Lucca.

Doernberg A, Horn P, Zasada I, et al. (2019) Urban food policies in German city regions: An overview of key players and policy instruments. *Food Policy* 89: 101782. DOI: 10.1016/j.foodpol.2019.101782.

Grasseni C (2018) Food Citizenship? Collective Food Procurement in European Cities. *Europe Now*. Special feature on Food, Food Systems, and Agriculture.

Klebl F, Walthall B and Vicente-Vicente JL (2022) Planning for sustainable food communities: An optimal spatial allocation study of food hubs considering the 15-min city concept—The case of LebensMittelPunkte in Berlin. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems* 6. Available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fsufs.2022.913412> (accessed 29 August 2023).

López Cifuentes M, Freyer B, Sonnino R, et al. (2021) Embedding sustainable diets into urban food strategies: A multi-actor approach. *Geoforum* 122: 11–21. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoforum.2021.03.006.

Mendes W and Sonnino R (2018) Urban food governance in the global north. In: *The Sage Handbook of Nature: Three Volume Set*. Sage Publications Ltd., pp. 543–560.

Mooney PH (2022) Local governance of a field in transition: The food policy council movement. *Journal of Rural Studies* 89: 98–109. DOI: 10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.11.013.

Moragues-Faus A (2021) The emergence of city food networks: Rescaling the impact of urban food policies. *Food Policy* 103. Urban food policies for a sustainable and just future: 102107. DOI: 10.1016/j.foodpol.2021.102107.

Morgan K (2015) Nourishing the city: The rise of the urban food question in the Global North. *Urban Studies* 52(8): 1379–1394. DOI: 10.1177/0042098014534902.

Pusceddu AM (2022) The Moral Economy of Charity: Advice and Redistribution in Italian Caritas Welfare Bureaucracy. *Ethnos* 87(1). Routledge: 168–187. DOI: 10.1080/00141844.2019.1687538.

Sibbing LV and Candel JJL (2020) Realizing urban food policy: a discursive institutionalist analysis of Ede municipality. *Food Security*. DOI: 10.1007/s12571-020-01126-8.

Sonnino R (2019) Translating sustainable diets into practice: the potential of public food procurement. *Redes* 24(1): 14–29. DOI: 10.17058/redes.v24i1.13036.

Sonnino R and Milbourne P (2022) Food system transformation: a progressive place-based approach. *Local Environment* 27(7). Routledge: 915–926.

Vicente-Vicente JL, Borderieux J, Martens K, et al. (2023) Scaling agroecology for food system transformation in metropolitan areas: Agroecological characterization and role of knowledge in community-supported agriculture farms connected to a food hub in Berlin, Germany. *Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems* 47(6). Taylor & Francis: 857–889. DOI: 10.1080/21683565.2023.2187003.

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